

The Idaean syndrome

V

5. Introduction	2
5.1. <i>*-ka-</i> as element of Anatolian onomastics	3
5.2. <i>Gūgu/Kuka/Gyges</i>	4
5.3. The Hittite god Ḫašamili and the Hundred-hander Gyges	8
5.1. <i>kaka-</i> , “tooth”	12
5.2. A few insights into the semantics of <i>*-ka-</i>	14
5.3. <i>neka-</i> , <i>nekna-</i> , <i>kaina-</i> , a reconsideration	17
Abbreviations	19
Bibliography	20

5. Introduction

Evidence of Carian help during Gyges' rise¹ to power has often suggested he was Carian by birth.² Yet, given his established links to Mysia mentioned earlier (2.1), we should consider whether his name itself indicates a different identity. After noting that *Adamas* in Phrygia or Mysia forms a meaningful pair with *Idamas* in Lycia,³ I argued that Greek mythology helped spread the fame of the Daktyls — mysterious male and female beings known as *goētes*⁴ — who were masters of metallurgy⁵ and magic on Mt. Ida. The first challenge in supporting my claim was to identify a significant thread in Anatolian onomastics. In fact, the various PNN that contain *Ida-* as the first element suggest that the memory of the Cretan or Mysian Ida in Anatolia was a strong motivation for assigning such names, in accordance with a generally recognised principle that Neumann (1994b 128) has established for Mycenaean names:

Die Mykener pflegten - wie viele Volker damals und heute - ihren Kindern 'Wunschnamen' beizulegen, Namen, die die Ideologie dieser Gesellschaft erkennen lassen.⁶

Despite the difficulty of interpreting most of them, the list of epichoric PNN with *Ida-* or *d-* as the first component⁷ seems to confirm that the above principle also applies to names such as the Carian *Dquq* or *Idagygos* in Greek transmission.⁸ For a comprehensive understanding of the current state of research from a linguistic perspective, it is advisable to begin with the questions raised by Z. Simon (2019 296–297) concerning these and related names:⁹

Das Wort γυγαί ist aus einer Glosse von Hesychios bekannt, die praktisch immer zu πάπποι, 'Großväter' emendiert und mit heth. *huhha-*, keilschriftl. *hūha-* und lyk. *xuge-* (gleicher Bedeutung) verknüpft wird. Dieser Gruppe kann jetzt auch kar. *quq-* (ebenfalls 'Großvater') hinzugefügt werden (Adiego 2007a: 334, 408). [...] γυγαί stellt daher eine perfekte formale Entsprechung zu kar. *quq* dar. Semantisch ist die Entsprechung allerdings nicht so unproblematisch *šrquq*. Das karische Wort wurde aus Personennamen (*quq* / Γυγος; *dquq* / Ἰδαγυγος; *šrquq*) erschlossen (Adiego 2007a: 408), wobei fraglich bleibt, was diese Namen ursprünglich bedeuteten und ob die Bedeutung 'Großvater' tatsächlich zutrifft. (Die Bedeutung des Kompositionsglieds *d-* / Ἰδα- ist unbekannt (wobei die Interpretation 'grandfather of Ida' von Melchert 2013: keinen Sinn macht), die von *š(a)r-* ist etwa 'oben, ober-', vgl. Adiego 2007a: 340, 416, 419 mit Lit.).

As Z. Simon's arguments demonstrate, attempts to interpret the epichoric equivalents of the PN *Gyges* have been unsuccessful, mainly because they do not provide semantic coherence for compounds such as *dquq*/Ἰδαγυγος, whose meaning remains unclear unless we assume that the first element, *d-/Ἰδα-*, refers to Mt. Ida, as I have tried to show.

A key challenge in reinterpreting *Gyges* is overcoming its usual derivation from a kinship term (Oettinger 2021 120):

The etymology of the PN *Kuka-* is PIE **h₂auh₂o-*, continued by Latin *avus* and Hitt. *huhha-* 'grandfather', with lenition also in Luw. *hūha-*, Lyc. *xuga-*.

¹ Cf. Lavelle (1997 240 and n. 29, 252–253); Högemann and Oettinger (2018 170 and n. 125); Leloux (2018 181); Saviano (2017–2018 201).

² Cf. Adiego (2007 334–335): "I now have little doubt that the name of the Lydian king Γύγης must have the same origin. The problem posed by the phonetics (Lydian does not conserve PIE laryngeal **h₂*, unlike the other Anatolian dialects) can be overcome if we imagine the name to have a *Carian* origin"; Valério and Yakubovich (2022 348–349); Iancu (2023); Valério and Adiego (2024 523).

³ KPN 192, § 451-8 (Arsada). Cf. Berranger (1983).

⁴ Blakely (2006, 2007).

⁵ Pliny, *HN* 7.197: "ferrum Hesiodus in Creta eos qui vocati sunt Dactyli Idaei." The persistent ambiguity of "Ida" as Cretan or Mysian mountain does not invalidate the solidity of the Anatolian tradition, which is reinforced by the Homeric epos. Cf. Mackie (2014); Külzer (2020).

⁶ Cf. Palaima (1999).

⁷ See section 1.1; LGPN VB 208; Bettarini (2014 52).

⁸ Lloyd-Jones (1999); Gagné (2006); Bremmer (2009); Santini (2016, 2017).

⁹ Cf. Simon (2022); Bauer et al. (2024).

As noted by S. Zsolt, when the supposed Luvic equivalents of the Greek *Gyges* appear within a composite name, such as the Carian *šrqūq*, they seem to undermine the commonly accepted interpretation of the personal name as meaning “grandfather.”

An alternative perspective can be gained through *kukalim* — a legend inscribed on Lydian coins featuring a lion’s head¹⁰ — provided we consider it together with *walwete-*, whose numismatic attestation has suggested an equation with the Greek *Alyattes* (Ἀλυάττης) (Bauer et al. 2022). In this context, it has been proposed that “by the legend KUKALIM Alyattes declared himself as belonging to the dynasty of *Kuka-* (Gyges), the first of the Mermnad line” (Oettinger 2021 3) or that it translates as “I (am) (the son/descendant) of Kukas” (Dale 2015 157).¹¹

Building on my previous suggestion regarding Lydian *astrko-/asturko-* (2.2, 4.1) — interpreted as “daimon of the royal seat, i.e. Artemis” — *kukalim* can be parsed as *ku-ka-li-m*. If **ku-* means “god” and **-ka-* “offspring”, with *-li-* forming a possessive adjective in Lydian, then *kukalim* translates as “I am of divine offspring.” Leaving the second assumption to be addressed shortly, my preliminary conclusion is that even in the name of Gyges, a particular self-conceit is present, namely the idea of divine descent. Based on what Euler and Sasseville (2019 136ff.) have claimed about the deification of the Lydian king Croesus,¹² can we argue for a trend that began with the first Mermnad king?

Considering that Gyges in the Platonic version of his myth is endowed with the ring of invisibility, said to make its owner “equal to a god” (*isothēon*, *Rep.* 2.360c),¹³ we can assume the same applies to the Lydian king as the prototype of the tyrant, whom Euripides describes in the same way (*Tr.* 1169)? When Gyges dons the ring, it grants him the power to act among men as if he were a god, effectively making him a tyrant. Is there sufficient evidence to infer that Plato adapted the Gyges myth in a way that was deliberately inspired by the Lydian meaning of the king’s name?

5.1. **-ka-* as element of Anatolian onomastics

A key part of my hypothesis is that **kuka-* might be a Lydian word, even though it is attested only within the compound *kukalim*, which is commonly read as a patronymic.¹⁴ But what about **-ka-*? To prove that it may convey a meaning such as “offspring,” a useful point of comparison is Hittite *Taruka*.¹⁵ This GN appears to be formed from *Taru-* — a theonym¹⁶ — with the addition of *-ka*,¹⁷ though whether this is a suffix or a nominal stem remains unknown.

¹⁰ Karwiese (1991 249–253); Wallace (2006); Konuk and Kerschner (2020 111).

¹¹ Cf. Dale (2020 518–520). On the different interpretations of this Lydian formation, Gusmani (1972), Melchert (1991 138 n. 14).

¹² Cf. Yakubovich (2024).

¹³ “Now if there were two such rings, and the just man would put one on, and the unjust man the other, no one, as it would seem, would be so adamant as to stick by justice and bring himself to keep away from what belongs to others and not lay hold of it, although he had license to take what he wanted from the market without fear, and to go into houses and have intercourse with whomever he wanted, and to slay or release from bonds whomever he wanted, and to do other things as an equal to a god among humans.” (Bloom 1991 38, 2.360b–c). Cf. Laird (2001).

¹⁴ LW II 90. Cf. Carruba (1964 275–276); Neumann (1969 224 and n. 23); Zgusta (1970 91); Lipiński (1975 158–159); Mouton and Yakubovich (2019 220); Martínez-Rodríguez (2025 165). *Contra* Gusmani, LW I 196: “Man kann ferner darauf hinweisen, daß die sicheren Ethnika eine andere Bildungsweise zeigen (s. *ibšimsi-*).” These attempts are basically focused on the Lydian *silukali-*, virtually the possessive adjective of **siluka*, and the village Sillyon in the vicinity of Smyrna (Fontrier 1892 403 and n. 1) could provide a clue. On Sillyon, KON 569, § 1216-3; SB IV 181; Nollé (1991 333 and n. 14).

¹⁵ RGTC VI/2 163.

¹⁶ Gessel (1998–2001 442ff.).

¹⁷ Forlanini (1987 108): “Prenons l’exemple du dieu *Taru* et des trois villes de *Tarukka*, *Ta/uḫamutaru* et *Dahattaruna*. Dans le cas de *Tarukka* on a supposé un suffixe *-(k)ka*.”

The same could be said for *Širika*,¹⁸ another Hittite place name.¹⁹ In fact, *Širika* can be parsed as *Širi-/Šeri-* + *-ka-*: the combination of a Hurrian theonym²⁰ with a morpheme frequently found in Anatolian GNN, such as *Hilika*,²¹ a well-known Iron Age toponym about which G. Neumann (1979 435) has made the following remarks:

Der Orts- und Bereichsname *Hilikka* (mit Varianten) ist also sicher indigen-kleinasiatisch; ob hethitisch/luwisch oder vorhethitisch, muß unentschieden bleiben. Ortsnamen mit *-kk-* in der letzten Silbe finden sich in den hethitischen Keilschrifttexten mehrfach: Arduka, Daruqqa, Hartakka, Hasiqqa, Nerikka, Serigga, Zahaluqqa. Das Nebeneinander von Nerik und Nerikka könnte nahelegen, die *Stämme* dieser Namen für vorhethitisch zu halten und mit einer sekundären Thematisierung (Überführung in die Klasse der *a*-Stämme) durch die Hethiter zu rechnen. Aber das bleibt hypothetisch.

In the case of *Hilika*, the status of *-ka* — whether suffix or noun — remains unresolved. The suffix hypothesis is supported by the Palaic *-iga*,²² yet, it cannot account for *Taruka*, *Arduka*,²³ *Daruqa*²⁴ and *Hartaka*.²⁵ On the other hand, treating **-ka* as a noun would explain the latter GNN, as well as *Šeri-ka* and *Išmiri-ka*, where the first element is a nominal *i*-stem. Before discussing the semantics and function of this nominal stem, I will first propose a new interpretation of the PN *Gyges*, likely the Greek rendition of the Lydian **kuka-*.

5.2. *Gūgu/Kuka/Gyges*

Gyges the Hundred-Hander (Hes. *Theog.* 149)²⁶ and *Gyges* the Lydian king are canonically distinguished by the length of the first syllable (West 1966 210), short for the former and long for the latter. However, as this rule allows exceptions²⁷ and the Lydian royal house is mythically connected to a breed of monsters through the Gygean lake (Γυγαίη λίμνη),²⁸ I would like to explore this ambiguity to assess whether a possible overlap is tenable.

The water reservoir, attested from Homer onwards (*Il.* 2.865, 20.390) and also known as *Koloē*, is mentioned by Strabo (13.4.7).²⁹ As thoroughly discussed by L. Robert (1982), it is linked with Echidna in Greek myth, a primordial sea-monster,³⁰ daughter of Kētō and Phorkys (Pherec. 3 F 7)³¹

¹⁸ RGTC VI 360; RGTC VI/2 146.

¹⁹ Cornelius (1958 393); Freu (2006 220); Novák and Rutishauser (2012 262–264); Forlanini (2013a 8 n. 32, 14–15, 19–20); J.D. Hawkins and Weeden (2017 282–283); Forlanini (2018 25).

²⁰ Cf. Trémouille (2001 67): “Aussi au point de vue linguistique, Kizzuwatna se présente comme une terre d’échange: sur le loup, qui est la langue de la population, se sont greffés des apports hourrites, mêlés d’éléments sémitiques, qui se sont lentement louvisés” and Dietz (2019 197–198). “Mentioned in addition to the divine weapons are a chariot, the two bulls Šeri and Hurri and, in some texts, the mountains. These are all aspects of depictions of the Storm-God of Aleppo in all media. I would be hesitant to apply this since the texts refer to the temple of Teššob in Hattuša.” Cf. Klengel (1965 90); Neu (1974 117); Haas (1994 471–472); Singer (1994 84); Popko (2002 78); Taracha (2008 749); Nicolle (2015 37–38, 58, 108, 381–382).

²¹ RGTC VI 108; RGTC VI/2 39.

²² Cf. Simon (2023).

²³ RGTC VI 40, s.v. *Artuka*.

²⁴ RGTC VI 408–409, s.v. *Taruka*.

²⁵ RGTC VI 91.

²⁶ Hard (2004 66): “The second group of monstrous sons of Earth and Sky consisted of three gigantic beings who each had fifty heads and a hundred arms; although Hesiod refers to them by their individual names alone, Cottos, Briareos, and Gyges mythographers in later times devised a convenient name for them, calling them the HEKATON-CHEIRES or HUNDRED-HANDERS (the corresponding adjective is already applied to Briareos in the *Iliad*).”

²⁷ Cairns (1995 85–91).

²⁸ KH 59. Cf. Mitten and Yügrüm (1971); Li Gotti Macri (1976); Talamo (1979 39–40); Roosevelt (2009 44, 99–100, 123–124); Dale (2020 519 n. 4): “Whether Γυγαίη is in origin an adjective (‘the Gygean lake’) or a noun (‘the lake Gygaie’) is unclear (though Strabo 13.4.5 uses Γυγαίη unambiguously as a noun), but it was evidently understood as the former by the Romans (e.g. Prop. 3.11 *Lydia Gygaeo tincta puella lacu*, and cf. Plin. *HN* 5.111), whence our familiar ‘Gygean lake’.”

²⁹ Str. 13.4.7: “Lying around Lake Koloe are the memorials of the kings.”

³⁰ Visintin (2000); Baglioni (2017).

³¹ Dolcetti (2004 151).

and wife of Typhōeus in Arimoi (Hes. *Theog.* 297-304, Hdt. 4.9).³² Unfortunately, we do not know where this is located, nor whether the name of the lake is derived from the king or from the Hundred-Hander (Roosevelt 2009 124):

Homer's referral to *Gygaia limne* probably predates the famous Mermnad Gyges and thus the name must derive from the common root of *Gygaia* and *Gyges*: a cognate to the Luwian *Huha* and the Lycian *Kuga*, both meaning “grandfather,” “ancestor,” or “old one.” The adoption of this ancestral name for the lake may derive from the fact that, by the Early Iron Age, the area of central Lydia around the Gygaean Lake had been inhabited far longer and had far more noticeable remains of earlier occupation than anywhere else in central Lydia (see Chapter 2).

This essay, based on the Lydian **kuka-* and building on the findings of previous articles in this series, proposes an alternative interpretation to that summarised above, possibly aiming to account for both *Gyges*. A reference to this PN can explain the hydronym's etymology if we identify **kuka-* as a compound of two segments, indicating that the lake was inhabited by the offspring (**ka-*) of god/goddess (**ku-*).

Given that we are here limited to what has been preserved of Anatolian mythology in Greek tradition, Kētō is the ideal avatar in Anatolia, not only linguistically — in light of the Mysian ethnic Κήτριοι (*Od.* 11.521) and the hydronym Κήτριος (KH 79) — but also because the Homeric myth connects the Maionian leaders to a lake that is the lair of Echidna, daughter of Kētō. The hydronym Γυγαίη can thus be understood within a reasonable semantic framework, namely as referring to **kuka-*, the “offspring of the goddess” which originated there.³³

In Greek mythology, the Hundred-Hander Gyges is known from Hesiod's *Theogony* (149, 618, 713, 734, 817), in which he, along with Kottos and Briareus, is described as a helper of Zeus in the succession myth — the struggle against the Titans. Although we must postpone the attempt to identify a possible vehicle for the transmission of the Anatolian core of the myth to Greek ears, we can find support for the hypothesis that *Gyges* is a rendition of **kuka-* in a linguistic annotation: Κολόη³⁴ is another name for the Gygean lake, which corresponds in Lydian to **kulu-* preserved in the ethnic *kulumv(i)-* “of Koloē.” If **kuka-* and **kulu-* share the same stem **ku-*, **kul(i)-* can be explained by the Lydian possessive suffix *-l(i)-*³⁵ and thus mean “divine.”

At this point, we could learn from the Lydian “neuter substantive *mru-*,” described as “a contracted variant of *mruwa-*” (Sasseville 2020 180), and assume that just as Nivónη³⁶ may reflect *Ninuwa* (Ninive)³⁷ in Greek transmission, so Κολόη < **kuluwa-*. However, although “Lyd. *-o-* may correspond to Luw. *-uwa-*” (Sasseville 2025),³⁸ another solution is at hand,³⁹ perhaps by considering what Rieken and Sasseville (2014) suggested regarding the equative suffix **-wo-*.⁴⁰ Along these lines,

³² Cf. West (1966 244); LGPN-Ling, *Gygaia*, [https://lgpn-ling.huma-num.fr/Gygaia].

³³ How such a general meaning may align with Γυγαία (Lyc. 1152) (Hornblower 2015 415), an epithet of Athena, or with the GN Γύγας (Str.13.1.22), a promontory on the coast of the Troad near Dardanos (TIB XIII 525, s.v. *Dardanos Akra*; (Borza et al. 2026)), requires further investigation.

³⁴ KON 277-278, § 554.

³⁵ Melchert (2012a 280): “The Lydian possessive adjective in *-l(i)-* reflects PIE denominative **(o)lo-* (well attested in Hittite as a derivational suffix).” Cf. Gérard (2005 89).

³⁶ SB III 387, § 62; KON 424-425, § 898-1; Blümel (1998–2012 177). Cf. L. Robert (1980 332–334); Brody (2001 101–102); Chanotis (2010 239–240); Van Bremen (2010 442); Özgümüş (2014); Chanotis and Rojas (2016 342).

³⁷ Laroche (1959 130); Gessel (1998–2001 941–942); Melchert (2024 165). Zgusta rightly compares Nivónη to *Ninuwa*: “Man vergleiche den keilschriftlichen ON Ninuwa, belegt bei Ertem, Dizin 103 (Literatur).”

³⁸ Cf. LW II 104-105.

³⁹ Melchert (2021 114): “Likewise, Lydian ⟨u⟩ is often equivalent to Greek omicron, as in *kulu-* for Κολόη (see Gérard 2005: 34).”

⁴⁰ Yakubovich's analysis (2021 237–238) of Lydian *ēnwala-* may be pertinent here. Cf. Yakubovich (2026a): “As stressed in Yakubovich 2010b:380 and Rieken & Sasseville 2014a:307, the second part of Hitt./Luw. *anna-wali-* must be considered together with Luw. *aya-wala-* ‘(a representative of the king)’.” Cf. Melchert (2024 44), s.v. **ayawali-* “(an) equal”: “For derivation via **wo-(o)lo-* see Rieken & Sasseville, *FsOettinger* 306, citing Melchert (p. c.) for root equation with Latin *ae-quus*.” According to Rieken and Yakubovich (2022 277) HLuw. *alumn(i)-* can be traced back to **al-wo-* meaning “sozial nicht zur eigenen Sphäre gehörig,” “feindlich” via the so-called “equative” suffix **-wo-*. This

**kul(i)-* + **-wo-* > **kulu-*⁴¹ meaning “godlike” is a plausible scenario, and Κολών could simply be the result of “féminisation”⁴² in Greek transmission.

Unexpected support for the hypothesis advanced so far about **kulu-* as “godlike” comes from the Greek term κολοσσός, “statue, *s.times usu.* depiction, image” (MGS),⁴³ which can be transparently traced back to a formation with the Common Anatolian possessive suffix *-(a)ssa/i-*⁴⁴ and mean “that which is godlike.”

This semantic scenario helps clarify the main thread of Herodotos’ account (2.143.2-144.1)⁴⁵ on the Egyptian *kolossoi*, or at least why this philologically problematic *logos* (Bravo 2009) emphasises that “all whose statues stood there had been good men, but wholly unlike gods.”⁴⁶ Was he implicitly commenting on the original meaning of a word borrowed from Anatolia, which meant exactly the opposite of what he argued against Hecataeos, who “had traced his descent and claimed that his sixteenth forefather was a god” (2.143.4)? In other words, the unspoken aspect of his polemical stance may depend on silencing the echo of the word *kolossos*, while being aware of its original meaning. Far from being “godlike” (θεῶν δὲ πολλὸν ἀπαλλαγμένους, Hdt. 2.144.1),⁴⁷ *kolossoi*, despite their association with the height of “colossal” statues,⁴⁸ are merely images.

Furthermore, additional and perhaps decisive support for my interpretation of **ku-* as “daimon, god” can be found in “Luw. *kumma-*, Lyc. *kuma-* and congeners”⁴⁹ which could be interpreted as denominal adjectives basically meaning “divine.”⁵⁰ In his latest suggestion regarding a possible etymology of CLuw. *kumma-* “pure, sacred,” Melchert (2024 116)⁵¹ refers to a virtual **kubh-* “bright, white.”⁵² However, *kumma-* may be derived from **ku-* “daimon, god” and mean “having a daimon,” as seen in “CLuv. *pihamma/i-* (= HLuv. /*pihamma/i-/*) and *pihaimma/i-* ‘imbued with splendor/might’ ← *piha-* ‘splendor/might’” (Melchert 2014a 207).

The relationship between the concept of “holy, holiness” and that of “fullness” has been emphasised by Polomé and Mallory (1997 493), referring to PIE root **k^hueh₁* (IEW 592-4, LIV² 340-341):

interpretation has been accepted by Melchert (2019 370 n. 39) for the Hittite *alwanza-*: “the Hittite is more economically derived directly from a base **al-wo-* with Rieken – Sasseville 2014: 306.”

⁴¹ Cf. Benveniste (1932a 123–124), who lists likely reflexes of this stem in Greek onomastics. Cf. Kronasser (1960).

⁴² Cf. LGPN-Ling, *Chrysothoē*, [https://lgpn-ling.huma-num.fr/Chrysothoē].

⁴³ Chantraine (1931); Benveniste (1932a, 1932b); Roux (1960); Servais (1965); Ducat (1976); Dickie (1996); Vernant (2006); Sichelschmidt (2019 36–37).

⁴⁴ Melchert (2012a 282). Benveniste’s analysis (1932a 118, 123), which segmented *kolossos* as *kulu-* plus the Luwian suffix *-ssos*, has been widely accepted.

⁴⁵ Di Bella (2018); Rignanese (2018); Zehner (2024).

⁴⁶ Godley (1975 451). Cf. Detienne (1986 75).

⁴⁷ Ingarao (2020 258): “I sacerdoti *contrapposero* a quella di Ecateo *una genealogia basata sul calcolo*, rifiutando tra l’altro l’idea che un *uomo potesse nascere da un dio*. I conti dei sacerdoti egizi, ai quali anche in questo caso viene fatto riferimento in modo insistito, uniti all’*ergon*, rappresentato dagli innumerevoli *agalmata*, sembrano costituire prove credibili e determinanti. In effetti lo storico aggiunge nel capitolo successivo che ha visto le statue e coloro che erano rappresentati avevano aspetto umano, o meglio “erano molto distanti dagli dei” (θεῶν δὲ πολλὸν ἀπαλλαγμένους). Secondo gli Egizi, invece, in un tempo ancora precedente, gli dei avrebbero governato l’Egitto vivendo insieme agli uomini e alternandosi al potere, fino a Dioniso/Osiride che può essere considerato l’ultimo sovrano.”

⁴⁸ Roux (1960 7): “A l’origine, le mot est absolument indépendant de la taille de la statue qu’il désigne et c’est le colosse de Rhodes qui lui donna par la suite son sens ‘colossal’.” Cf. Cancik (1990).

⁴⁹ Payne, Bauer, Rieken, et al. (2026). Cf. Melchert (1997 50).

⁵⁰ Melchert (2014a 206–207). Cf. Goedegebuure (2024 58) and Simon (2026), s.v. Carian **urom* > **u/wrm*: “if we assume a substantivization of *ura-* (*‘the great one’), then both formally fitting denominal suffixes, the appurtenance suffix *-ama/i-* (hence *‘pertaining to the great one’) and the possessive adjective suffix *-mma/i-* (hence *‘having the great one’) can provide a solution, although the semantics of the latter solution is less fitting in my view.”

⁵¹ “Rather < virtual **koubh-mo-* to **kubh-* ‘bright, white’; for sense cp. Arm. *surb* ‘pure’.” Cf. Stempel (1987); Morani (2001 169, 182 and n. 25, 195); Jurczyk (2022); Drigo (2024 118–119).

⁵² Cf. Valério and Adiego (2024 515 n. 6), from a personal communication by Melchert: “Luwian *kumma-* ‘pure, sacred’ from a reconstructed form **koubh-mo-* < **kubh-* ‘bright, white’ (for the sense, compare Arm. *surb* ‘pure’).”

Another major concept involved with the sacred is ‘wholeness’ which may be seen in **k̂uen(to)-* where its derivation from **k̂eu(hi)-* ‘swell’ also indicates ‘fullness, complete’ and a similar connotation can be found in **h_aéuges-* ‘fullness of sacred power’.

Perhaps this annotation opens a path to the common etymology of the Greek κολοσσός and κύρος (“supreme power, absolute authority,” MGS) or κύριος (“having power, *or* authority, lord, master,” MGS),⁵³ all possibly referring to **k̂ueh₁* (Beekes and Beek 2010 806–807). If the latter is the root that can account for the virtual Lydian **ku-* as “daimon, god” and **kul-* as “divine,” as well as PNN such as the Lycian Κολαλημῆς⁵⁴ and Cilician Κολαμοαῶς⁵⁵ or Κολαρβασίς,⁵⁶ we may even consider that we are dealing with a Common Anatolian root.

As for the latter PN, since the name of Erbbina⁵⁷ — the Lycian king of the first decades of the 4th century — can be parsed as **erbbi-* + *-na/i* (< **-ñna/i-*),⁵⁸ it could be derived from **Erbi-*, like *Tlãñna-* from *Tla-* “Tlos” (DLL 68).⁵⁹ Thus, *Erbbina* could be “the substantivization in *-a-*”⁶⁰ of **erpini-* (< **(w)arpini-*),⁶¹ the Lycian cognate of CLuw. *warpanni(i)-*,⁶² in which the suffix *-anni*⁶³ probably has a possessive meaning, so that it could mean “having a weapon,” but a special one, the deified weapon of Trqqas.⁶⁴ This would provide a clue to explain also the Lycian B *erbbesi*⁶⁵ and the Cilician PN Τροκοαρβασίς.⁶⁶

Adiego (2022 83–84) has come to the following conclusion in view of two epithets of Trqqas/Trqqiz associated in TL 44 d 12–13:

Here, *esetesi* and *erbbesi* are epithets of the god Tarhunt- (*Trqqiz* in Milyan), formed by means of the possessive adjective **-ass-i-* on *esete-* and *erbbe-* respectively, so the sequence means ‘Tarhunt- of the *esete-* and the *erbbe-*’, ‘Tarhunt of the victory/peace/...(?) and of the defeat/turmoil/war ...(?)’. This passage bears witness to the existence of a formula in Milyan *Trqqiz erb[b]esi* (‘*Trqqñt-* of the *erbbe-*’)

⁵³ Garnier (2021 196ff.).

⁵⁴ KPN 240, § 657-1; LGPN VB 240. Cf. Brixhe and Gibson (1982 149); Schürr (2012 39); Adak (2013 75–76); Gürel, Akçay, and Önen (2019 420).

⁵⁵ LGPN VB 240.

⁵⁶ KPN 240, § 657-2; LGPN VB 240.

⁵⁷ Balzat (2014 268 n. 88): “*Erbbina*, the name borne by a famous Lycian dynast, was rendered in Greek by Αρβίνας (LGPN VB s. v. Αρβίνας [1]). The female name Ερβίνα (LGPN VB s. v. Ερβίνα [1]) is attested in an unpublished Greek inscription from Xanthos dated to the Roman imperial period. Whether the origin of the dynast’s name is Luwian or Iranian is debated (see Neumann, 66).” Cf. Konuk (2009); Müseler and Schürr (2018); Müseler (2019). Both Αρβίνας and Αρβίνας are attested in Greek transmission. Cf. Bousquet (1975); E. Hansen and Le Roy (1976); L. Robert (1978); Bousquet (1992). Schmitt (1982 378–379) for a possible Persian origin of the PN.

⁵⁸ Cf. NH 331-332; Kloekhorst (2008b 135–137); Borchhardt, Eichner, and Schulz (2005 36); Schürr (2021 19).

⁵⁹ Cf. *Pñtreñneli-* (DLL 51), on which Gusmani (1968 7) and Schürr (2016b 771–774).

⁶⁰ Sasseville (2024). Cf. Norbruis (2021 33 and n. 35, 120).

⁶¹ Cf. *erublije-* (DLL 17) ≈ *urublije-* (DLL 77). Billing (2024): “The forms with initial *u-* are taken here as variants of *erublije-* with total vowel harmony (cf. Meriggi 1978c:252).” Otherwise Schürr (2019 189): “Eine vergleichbare Dissimilation *uCu > eCu* gibt es bei *urublijē*, viermal in TL 44 (Xanthos), später *erublija* (Pl.) in TL 26, vielleicht nicht zufällig auch in Tlos, und dem Ortsnamen *Tuburehi* TL 44b, 15 (Tyberissos), auf dessen B-lykisches Ethnikon der Personennamen *Tebursseli* TL 103 und 104 zurückgehen wird (Schürr 2010, 125 im Anschluß an I. Yakubovich). Der Grund dafür konnte sein, da der erste Vokal unbetont war und daher nicht mehr deutlich artikuliert wurde.” Cf. LPG 197: “But to explain Lycian *erbbe-* as being Luwian *arpa-* presents greater difficulties.” For this generally accepted connection, HED I 169. Nonetheless: “Die Beziehung zu dem Glossenkeilwort *arpa-*, das eher ‘Mißerfolg’ bedeutet, ist unklar” (Schürr 2018 67).

⁶² CLL 260, s. v. *warpanna/i-*: “Should be diminutive to *warpi-*, but this does not illuminate context of occurrence.” Rieken (2022a). Cf. Yakubovich (2019 550).

⁶³ Yakubovich and Simon (2024): “The alternation between the variants */tawiyanni/* and */tawiyani/* is closely paralleled by the similar case of */parranni/* vs. */parrani/*, */appanni/* vs. */appani/*, and ultimately */anni/* vs. */anna/*. The optional apocope to */tawiyani/* is likely to have been possible already in the second millennium BCE, as demonstrated through cuneiform evidence.”

⁶⁴ Yakubovich (2019 549–551).

⁶⁵ Cf. Cilician Αρβασίς (KPN 88, § 85-1) and Κολαρβασίς (KPN 241, § 657-2), Carian Αρβησσις (§ 85-2) and Αρβησις (§ 85-3). DLL 115; GLyk 65; René Lebrun (1990 166–167); Neumann (1994a 151–153); Réveilhac (2024 481).

⁶⁶ Schürr (1997 65): “*Trqqiz* und *erbbesi* haben ein Echo in dem PN Τροκοαρβασίς (Kilikien, KPN § 1512-22). Das scheint alles zu sein.” Cf. Adiego (2007 334); Réveilhac (2023).

which corresponds exactly to the one we find in the name Τροκοαρβασις. [...] If this interpretation is accepted, then Τροκοαρβασις may include this formula expressed in the vocative: /Tarxu arbasi(s)!/ ‘O Tarhu(nt) of the defeat/turmoil (?)’, a sort of epiclesis or invocation.

If Erbbina is the Lycian king whose name evokes the mighty weapon of Trqqas, the same could apply to Ὀρβασις in Kibyrtis⁶⁷ or Οὐρβάσι[ος] in Isauria⁶⁸ — both derived from HLuw. *warpasi*-⁶⁹ — and to Ορπεννα,⁷⁰ a Lycian location about 14 km. northwest of Elmalı.

If we consider the two versions of the toponym, *Orpeēna* (?) and *Orpenna*, we find that its morphology may be explained with the Lycian suffix *-ēne/i-*, which — according to a suggestion by Rieken and Sasseville (2024) — “can also create adjectives” and make the two GNN cognates of CLuw. *warpann(i)-* (Melchert 2024 280).

As a first approximation of a possible trail leading from Koloē, the lair of Echidna — daughter of Kētō — and ideal centre of the Lydian royal descent, across the “Burnt Lands” (*Katakekaumene*),⁷¹ and in particular Satala,⁷² an ancient city in the volcanic area of Maionia, we follow the steps in mythology of Typhōeus, consort of Kētō.

At this point, we should pose a crucial question: if Gyges the king and Gyges the Hundred-hander belong together in a mythological complex where water and fire are united — the children of Kētō live in the sea abyss or in the depths of Gygaian Lake, but are also associated with volcanoes — is there anything in the myth of Gyges’ ascent to power that proves a similarity with the monster?

5.3. The Hittite god Ḫašamili and the Hundred-hander Gyges

As noted above, the only aspect of this myth that could qualify Gyges for a divine role, overlapping with that of the Hundred-hander, is the ring of invisibility,⁷³ which could also fit the finger of Ḫašamili, a Hittite deity⁷⁴ well known for protecting King Muršiliš II with a kind of invisibility shield,⁷⁵ as well as for what we learn from CTH 726.1 (§§ 2-4), a ritual in which he comes in after a smith has dug a trench (Torri 2011):⁷⁶

La dea Sole si costruì una casa e chiamò Kamrušepa. “Tu hai portato a compimento il palazzo!” e Kamrušepa dispose ciò che lei aveva compiuto. Ella chiamò il fabbro potente: “Orsù! Prendili, i chiodi

⁶⁷ LGPN VC 330. Cf. Réveilhac (2023 200).

⁶⁸ Feissel (2010 423–425).

⁶⁹ CHLI 509, 515; Giusfredi (2010 137); Balatti (2012 150–152); Rieken (2022b).

⁷⁰ KON 448, § 949; TIB VIII 768-769. Cf. ἐν Ορπηνοῖς (Bean 1971 27, § 48); J. Robert and Robert (1972 470): “le nom antique du lieu, Orpénoi ou Orpéna (ou Horpénoi, etc.)”; Wörrle (1988 13, 47); Strubbe (1997 242); Hild (2004 121); Foss et al. (2019).

⁷¹ Debord (1985); Daubner (2013).

⁷² L. Robert (1962 280–317); Chuvin (1991 105–106).

⁷³ Mehl (2003 248–250).

⁷⁴ Laroche (1946 23; 1973 88). Cf. Goetze (1962 49): “The god has been claimed as (Proto-)Ḫattic. This must be contested; the recurrence of the name in Alalah IV is decidedly against it. I assigned the deity to the Kanishites (Lang. 29, 1953, 269f.” Steitler (2017 183 n. 582): “The deity Ḫašamili does occur in Hattian contexts, but is also attested in texts from Kültepe in the PN *Ḫa-za-mi-il*₅ (JCS 74.14; kt d/k 40a-b; kt 94/k 362; kt d/k 28), though this DN might be considered part of the Hattian substrate there.”

⁷⁵ Houwink ten Cate (1966 165, 180); Hoffner (1980 314, 328); del Monte (1986 60–61); Pecchioli Daddi and Polvani (1990 67 and nn. 21, 23); Haas (2006 81, 117, 119; 2008 135). Van den Hout (2003 197–198): “I, the Great King, marched concealed with my troops and chariots. The mighty Storm-god, My Lord, had called for me Ḫašammili, My Lord, and he kept me concealed so that no one saw me.” Cf. CHD L–N 332, s.v. *munnai-*: “I, the great king, together with my troops and chariotry proceeded concealed. The mighty Stormgod, my lord, had summoned Ḫašammili, my lord, for me and he kept me hidden, (so that) no one saw me.”

⁷⁶ del Monte (2003 151); Oğuz Soysal and Aygül (2016 353, 356, 360); Della Casa (2019 492). Oğuz Soysal (2021 167): “Der Gott Ḫašamil(i) legt die Wünsche der Götter auf das Fundament des Gebäudes. [...] Die Funktion von Ḫašamil(i) wird in der Erzählung nicht unmittelbar ersichtlich. Auf Befehl der Göttin Kataḫzipuri/Kamrušepa bereitet ein sterblicher Schmiedemeister die Eisenpflocke bzw. Nägel sowie einen Kupferhammer vor und öffnet ein Loch im Erdboden, sodass der Gott Ḫašamil(i) in den Untergrund gehen und dort die Herzen, d. h. die Wünsche der Götter begraben kann.”

di ferro e il maglio di bronzo! Prendi il *kam*[-] di ferro e fendi la ter[ra!]”. Egli, il dio Ḥašammili, entrò e sotterrò (nella terra) il cuore degli dei. “Esso divenga [l’u]manità! Proprio gli dei fanno il paese e noi”.

Although often attributed with metallurgical expertise,⁷⁷ the deity is clearly associated only with obscurity,⁷⁸ night, invisibility, and with not being affected by the rather mysterious *ḥaḥḥima*- (Della Casa 2019 491–492):⁷⁹

Interestingly, the Sun-god’s *mugawar* (CTH 323), after *ḥaḥḥima*- seized ḏLamma and Telipinu, narrates that the god who was not seized was Ḥašamili, because his brothers were the brothers of *ḥaḥḥima*-. As a result of this statement, Ḥašamili becomes a key character in our effort to better understand the role of *ḥaḥḥima*-, since the emphasis put on their relationship seems to point to inner aspects they have in common. Unfortunately, Ḥašamili does not seem to be an easy character to unravel (see Otten 1972–1977: 127; Archi 1966: 89, 96–100; Archi 1975; Popko 1978: 22–23, 130–131).

What we know about Ḥašamili is that he is brother of *ḥaḥḥima*- (Hoffner 1988 196):⁸⁰

“Ḥašamili’s brothers were (Hahhimas’) brothers by the same father. (Therefore) Hahhimas did not seize them.”

Ḥašamili, according to Goetze (1953 270), “has to do with shutting out the light either of the sun or of the stars”⁸¹ and the so-called “wood of Ḥašamili”⁸² could have a cosmological significance, as the god appears untouched by the effects of the Sun’s disappearance.⁸³ Perhaps the key to a correct understanding of the role played by the deity in the two major attestations cited above can be inferred from CTH 398 § 5 (Collins 1990 212):⁸⁴

In the Hittite Ritual of Huwarlu, a puppy of tallow is used to protect the king and queen from evil: “[And] they make [a puppy of tallow, and they set it on the wood of the palace’s door bolt, and she (the old woman) says as follows: ‘You (are) the puppy of the table of the king and queen, and as by day you do not allow a strange person into the palace, on this night you must not allow in an evil word.’”

⁷⁷ Steitler (2019 128): “In this myth, which reports that the Sun-goddess built her house in the city of Liḫzina, the goddess Kamrušepa (in Hattian Kataḫzipuri) calls upon the ‘mighty smith’ who is subsequently identified as the god Ḥašamili.” Cf. Cordani (2016 167). *Contra* Oğuz Soysal (2021 167 n. 6): “Nach den verfügbaren Belegen hat der Gott Ḥašamil(i) weder etwas mit dem Bau noch mit dem Schmiedehandwerk zu tun.”

⁷⁸ Popko (1991 243): “Es sei daran erinnert, daß nach den Annalen Muršiliš der Gott Ḥašammili die Gabe besitzt, Menschen unsichtbar zu machen. Die Unsichtbarkeit steht mit der Dunkelheit in einem semantischen Zusammenhang, was das Nebeneinander beider Gottheiten im besagten Ritual teilweise verstehen läßt.” *Contra* Steitler (2023 167).

⁷⁹ De Vries (1967 9–15); Polvani (1991 72–73); Stivala (2004 47 and n. 52); Arroyo (2014 225–226); Dardano (2016 56 n. 28). Cf. Haas (1994 371): “*Die Dämonin Ḥaḥḥima*: Die die Menschheit, das Vieh und den Feldbau zerstörenden Kräfte der Natur verkörpert Ḥaḥḥima, die ‘Erstarrung’.” For a survey of the available interpretations, Steitler (2017 208–209 and nn. 662, 664).

⁸⁰ Hoffner and Beckman (1990 28): “Hasamili’s (full) brothers are (Frost’s) half brothers. So Frost did not seize them.” Cf. Hoffner and Melchert (2024 98).

⁸¹ Haas (1994 144): “Eine andere Reihung lautet: ‘Schicksalsgöttinnen, Herd, Ugur und Ugur von Ḥayasa, Mond, Stern(e), Nacht, Ḥašam(m)ili’ usw.” Cf. Archi (1966 98); Archi (1975 79): “il dio Ḥašamili, che ha la funzione di celare al nemico i movimenti dell’esercito ittita, sembra essere materializzato in un qualche oggetto atto a schermare la luce all’interno di un ambiente.”

⁸² Steitler (2020). Cf. Oğuz Soysal (2024 115) argues that it could refer to a tree and not only to a wood or a wooden object: “Als einen weiteren, mit einem Götternamen verbundenen Baum kennt man ḏḤašamiliyaš GIŠ (KUB 25.18 III 33’, IV 29’, V 22’; KUB 54.81 Vs.? 6’).”

⁸³ Taracha (2009 78): “There is a tiny fragment of the story about the disappearance of the Sun, written in the Old Script; later copies have allowed the beginning and ending of the text to be reconstructed, revealing an entirely different scheme from what was typical of this group of myths from later times. The motif of binding so characteristic of indigenous Anatolian magic is present here. The mysterious Ḥaḥḥima (personified Numbness/Frost?) paralyzed the land, dried the springs and imprisoned the War-god, Inar and Telipinu, who had been sent by the Storm-god in search of the Sun. The Storm-god’s hands were stuck to the (offering?) cup he held, and his feet too were caused to get stuck. Only the fate goddesses and Ḥašamili escaped the Ḥaḥḥima. The text breaks off in this place.”

⁸⁴ Bawanypeck (2016); Cf. Haas (1994 289–290; 2003 412); Strauss (2006 75): “Das Königspaar und der Palast werden mit einem kleinen Hund umschwenkt. Die in den Körpern von König und Königin sowie im Palast lokalisierten dämonischen Unheilstoffe sollen von den als besonders groß angepriesenen Gliedern des Hundes Besitz ergreifen.”

The mysterious “wood of Ḫašamili” could be the door-bolt that the god guards like a dog at night, protecting the house from malignant daimons.⁸⁵ His close ties with the underworld were already emphasised by Goetze (1953 269):⁸⁶

His chthonic nature is apparent from his association with Lelwaniš, who is equated with ^DEREŠKIGAL and with ^DALLATUM, both Mesopotamian of the netherworld.

The latter is the Babylonian goddess,⁸⁷ whose Hurrian counterpart is Allani, known as the “bolt of the Underworld.”⁸⁸ Lelwani, “the Hittite queen of the Underworld” (Archi 1993 4), takes part in the dialogue between the Stormgod⁸⁹ and the king preceding Ḫašamili’s intervention (CTH 726.1, indicating that the forces from the Netherworld cannot go unrestricted.⁹⁰ The problem now is to interpret what happens after “the smith makes a trench in the earth”: “The god Ḫašammili goes underground and he buries the hearts of the gods there” (Oğuz Soysal and Aygöl 2016 356). A valuable clue comes from the same author, in light of the Ortaköy version of CTH 726.1, in which the narrative of the Sun god building a house for himself in the town of Liḫzina serves as the mythic prototype. The end of the section about Ḫašamili epitomises this concept with a formula such as: “We do it (because/how) the gods did it” or “What we do now, the gods used to do back then.”⁹¹

Given the large debt of Hittite sources to Mesopotamian mythology, it is important to note that, according to the latter, dead gods inhabit the underworld, and the Sun god is their caretaker (Horowitz 1998 284). Apparently, the gods whose hearts Ḫašamili (Oğuz Soysal and Aygöl 2016 353) is committed to bury⁹² are the so-called “lower gods”⁹³ of the Hittite pantheon, which could have a Greek counterpart in the Titans,⁹⁴ kept in custody underground by the Hundred-handers (Hes. *Theog.* 732-735).

Leaving undecided whether the smith ordered to bring in nails in CTH 726.1 is a man or the deity Ḫašamili, what matters is that the latter is charged by Kamrušepa, the goddess of magic, to perform a rite closely analogous to that of Malli from Arzawa (Wright 1987 45–46):⁹⁵

⁸⁵ Archi (1966 89); Haas (1994): “Das Ritual der Beschwörerin Šušumanniga (KUB 7.1 Vs. III 29-36, Rs. IV 1 '-5', bearbeitet von H. Kronasser 1961, 162-164) wird angewandt, ‘wenn einer für ein Kind den Ḫašam(m)ili des Monats [beopfert].’ Zu diesem Zweck stellt er einen Opfertisch mit der Statuette des Ḫašam(m)ili vor das Fenster.” Cf. Fuscagni (2017).

⁸⁶ Steitler (2017 143): “Ḫašammili appears in the Hattian, Palaean and Kanešian panthea in various constellations of deities. He is likely a chthonic deity since he is attested in contexts together with Lelwani, the fate goddesses and Kataḫzipuri. Ḫašammili, furthermore, can be represented by an object of wood and may be connected with cultic practices performed in sacred groves.”

⁸⁷ Cf. Otten (1950); Einar von Schuler (1980–1983); Torri (1999).

⁸⁸ Archi (2002 22): “The proem, no. 11, opens with these words: ‘I will tell of Teššub, the g[reat] lord of Kummi, I will exalt the you[ng lady] Allani (who stays) at the bolt (that is, the gate) of the Earth.’ Cf. Hoffner and Beckman (1990 72–73); Haas (1994 405); Neu (1996 53); Ünal (1996 39–40); Campbell (2008 78 and n. 17).

⁸⁹ Cf. Mazoyer (2004 58): “Le dieu de l’Orage qui est un dieu du ciel est doté d’une activité chthonienne, puisqu’il jette les fondations dans le sol et qu’il est associé à Lelwani, la divinité du monde souterrain, qui est un dieu mâle à l’époque hattie comme le montre son épiclèse ‘le roi’ *katte*. Lelwani devient une déesse à partir de Hattušili III ou peut-être avant.”

⁹⁰ Oğuz Soysal and Aygöl (2016 352–353, 355–356, 360).

⁹¹ Oğuz Soysal (2021 170).

⁹² Oğuz Soysal (2021 167 n. 6): “Seine Beschäftigung bzw. Aufgabe in KBo 37.1 besteht lediglich darin, die Herzen (= Wünsche) der Götter auf das Fundament des Gebäudes niederzulegen.”

⁹³ Laroche (2016 393–398). Cf. Oettinger (1989/1990 86 n. 9); Archi (1990 115); García Trabazo (2024).

⁹⁴ Oettinger (1989/1990 95); Högemann (2000 27); Beckman (2004 312): “Long ago relegated to the Netherworld like the Greek Titans, the Primeval Deities included among their number gods who originally entered Hurrian religion from Mesopotamia.”

⁹⁵ In the ritual of Ḫantitaššu (Ünal 1996 30, 72–74), the Netherworld gods are released (Collins 2004 54): “In one of these rituals, the Hittite wise woman, Hantitassu describes her technique for aiding a petitioner in obtaining forgiveness from sin. When night falls, the petitioner digs a hole in the ground and slits the throat of a piglet, letting its blood flow into the pit. Grains and liquids are offered into the pit as well. The doors to the Underworld are symbolically opened and the divine images of the Underworld deities are set around the pit to draw the deities up from the earth. Finally they are invoked to plead with the Sun Goddess of the Earth, Queen of the Underworld on behalf of the petitioners so that his offense may be forgiven.”

This motif is evident in acts that seek to keep an evil from returning after it has been dispelled or to prevent it from having any effect in first place. [...] in the Malli ritual, cathartic materials loaded with evil are buried and secured in the ground with pegs to prevent the escape of the impurity.

Since Ḫašamili seems to belong to the Hattian religious tradition, it is noteworthy that the king is described in Hattian as the door-bolt (*ḫaluḫalu*)⁹⁶ of the land, in a simile that also applies to the mythological role of the Hundred-handers, who must expel the Titans from the world inhabited by humans and gods. If Gyges, the Lydian king, has a name derived from **kuka-* meaning “offspring of god/goddess,” then the homonymous Hundred-hander may have the same origin and role as the Hittite Ḫašamili, known for repelling threats from the Underworld.

If we now look back at the myth of Gyges as narrated by Plato, the steps of the shepherd who later becomes king lead underground to the world of the dead, where he finds “a hollow bronze horse” and “a corpse inside that looked larger than human size” (*Rep.* 359d).⁹⁷ This tale refers to a landscape beneath which a tomb may be hidden, thus resembling that of Koloē: around there Gyges — “offspring of god/goddess” — may have entered the Netherworld, following the trail of Ḫašamili in CTH 726.1.

“The giant-like stature of the dead body” (Olshin 2019 279) found by Gyges is likely reflected in the PN *Koloē* (the *Gygaia limne*). Its etymology, tentatively proposed in the previous section as **kul(i)- + *-wo- > *kulu-*, meaning “godlike,” together with that of the Greek *kolossos*, “that which is godlike,” may provide a reasonable background for the Platonic myth. As the area of Koloē is a funerary monumental site for the Lydian kings,⁹⁸ assuming that the discovery of the colossal (“godlike”) body occurred there would equate Gyges (< **kuka-* “offspring of god”) with Ḫašamili. The latter god is the one who goes underground by order of Kamrušepa, the deity of magic, to control the “former gods” and also grants the privilege of invisibility to King Muršiliš II. Gyges’ magical initiation follows the same steps: to become *de facto* “equal to a god” (*isotheon*, *Rep.* 2.360c), which he already is *de nomine* (“offspring of god”), he must obtain the ring of the giant, a figure who, by virtue of being *kolossos* (“godlike”), is entitled to play the role of Ḫašamili towards a future king.

As seen above, CTH 323.1 establishes family ties between Ḫašamili to Ḫaḫḫima (*pappanegna-*, “brothers having the same father”),⁹⁹ making Johannes Lydus’s account (4.3) of Briareos, another Hundred-Hander, relevant (Hooker 2017 58–59):¹⁰⁰

The consul would offer his horse to Zeus [i.e., Jupiter]—for indeed, [he is] Helios himself, according to Pherecydes—and then, from there taking up the consular garment, would go forward. This [was done]

⁹⁶ Girbal (2002 262–263). Cf. Haas (2003 700–701).

⁹⁷ Bloom (1991 37).

⁹⁸ Rojas (2016 198): “At least since the mid-sixth century BC, the Gygaean Lake, the greatest of all Lydian bodies of water, was intimately associated with the historical Lydian kings. It was then that a huge earthen mound—about 70 meters high and 361 meters in diameter—was erected as the funerary monument for the historical Lydian king Alyattes (fig. 12.5). The Greek historian Herodotos was so impressed by this manmade mountain-tomb that he deemed it one of only two things worthy of wonder in all of Lydia (the other being the naturally gold-bearing Paktolos River). To this day, the tomb of Alyattes and indeed the entire tumulus cemetery that grew around it, which is known as Bin Tepe (Thousand Mounds), offer striking physical evidence of the close connection between the great lake and the Lydian kings. However, the name ‘Gygaean’ and the archaeological remains on the lake shores offer clues about the striated landscape that the kings co-opted with their funerary mounds.” Cf. Roosevelt (2009 44, 99–100, 123–124).

⁹⁹ CTH 323.1, § 8'. Rieken et al. (2009 n. 27): “Siehe CHD P 97a: ‘brother sharing the same father, paternal brother’. Vgl. dort die Übersetzung: ‘The brothers of Ḫašammili were (Ḫ.’s?) paternal brothers, (therefore) Ḫaḫḫima did not seize them.’” Cf. Bauer et al. (2014 153): “Seine, des Ḫašamili Brüder (sind seine) [Halbbr]üder, und die Starre ergriff sie nicht.”

¹⁰⁰ Cf. scholia to Hesiod, *Theogony* 148 (Cassanmagnago 2009 503): “Non degni di essere nominati’: ovvero quelli che uno non può nominare, terribili. Riporta nondimeno i loro nomi. E dice Cotto la forza cinetica, da ‘provare collera (kotein)’, Briareo la possanza, Gige la forza potenziale. Costoro sono detti venti che prorompono dalle nubi, e sono di sicuro devastatori. Per questo miticamente sono provvisti anche di cento braccia, perché hanno pulsionalità guerresca. Cotto, Briareo e Gige sono i tre momenti (dell’anno): Cotto è la collera della canicola, cioè il momento dell’estate; Briareo è la primavera, in rapporto con il fiorire (‘bryein’) e crescere delle piante; Gige è il tempo invernale. Costoro chiama anche dalle cento braccia o centimani, per il fatto che hanno molte energie. Omero (*Il.* 402-3) chiama Briareo centimano proprio per questo.”

in honor of Zeus, as it were because the giants had struggled against him—meaning, the winter weather was defeated by the sun. But the mythologists call the winter “Briareus,” a many-handed [being], on account of the fact that moisture streams forth in it in multiple ways; and at one time Briareus fights with Zeus (i.e., the sun), and then again becomes his ally, because the moist substance is allied with the warm.

At this point, as the real identity of the Hittite Ḫaḫḫima remains uncertain, and while Ḫašamili’s connection with metallurgy is possible, I am inclined to reject Johannes Lydus’s association between Briareos and winter, preferring instead to follow the trail of the fire-breathing Thyphoeus, who is well attested in Lydia.¹⁰¹ Without addressing here the question of a possible relationship between the Lemnian Kadmilos/Kasmilos and the Hittite deity Ḫašamili (Rutherford 2020 188–189),¹⁰² it is important to note that the network of monsters extends beyond Lydia proper, westward to Gergis in the Troad and the sphinxes depicted on its coins (SB I 419, § 58), as well as to Troy and the unnamed ketos menacing Hesione, the daughter of Laomedon, Priam’s father (West 2011 33):

Laomedon was an arrogant and tight-fisted king. Poseidon and Apollo spent a year in his service, fortifying his city for him, and he then sent them away unpaid with contumacious threats (*H* 452 f., *Φ* 442–57). He behaved similarly towards Heracles. After promising him some of his horses if he would come and deliver the Trojans from the depredations of a sea monster, he failed to hand them over and abused the hero, who retaliated by wrecking the city (*E* 638–51, *Y* 145–8). The fuller story was related by Hellanicus of Lesbos (fr. 26 Fowler). The monster had been sent by Poseidon in his anger against Laomedon. The king consulted an oracle and was advised to put out his daughter Hesione for the monster to devour. He did so, while promising his immortal horses to anyone who would dispatch the monster. Heracles accomplished this, but Laomedon then cheated him by giving him mortal horses instead of the immortal ones. Heracles discovered the deception, attacked Ilios and sacked it, and so got the horses he wanted.

Although I cannot pursue this route further, the upcoming discussion may help introduce some work tracks. For now, I add only that east of the Sea of Marmara, on Besbikos island, Briareos’s tomb and a gigantomachy are associated (Cuypers 2018), perhaps suggesting that the progress of Greek colonisation followed a path already traced by Anatolian mythology.¹⁰³

5.1. *kaka-*, “tooth”

Lacking an established etymology, the Hittite *kaka-*, “tooth,” can possibly be interpreted as an iterative base, much like *lāla-*, “tongue”¹⁰⁴ Taking the Sanskrit *dvijā*, “tooth,” literally “twice born”¹⁰⁵ as a conceptual model, **ka-* may be derived from PIE **ǵejH-* (LIV² 161), “aufbrechen, keimen” (IEW 355-6).¹⁰⁶ This aligns with the “eruption” of a tooth emerging from the gums, as envisaged by Hoffner for the Hittite hapax *kaki-* (2000 70):

kaki- may be *kaka-* “tooth” with a different stem vowel. If the *šuppiwašhar* is a head of garlic, peeling it back to its core would produce tooth-like cloves.

Hoffner (1996 250) links *kaki-* to a garlic clove, “which looks like a canine tooth,”¹⁰⁷ This mirrors the botanical metaphors of the German *Sproß* and French *rejeton*, suggesting *ka-ka-* literally means “twice-grown.”

¹⁰¹ Cf. Callimachus Fragment 1.36, Hunter and Laemmle (2019 495): “As has long been recognized, Callimachus not only here names the Giant as the hundred-hander Briareus (or Braireos), but also alludes in line 141 (τυρομένοιο) to the identification of the giant as Typhos or Typhoeus.”

¹⁰² Cf. Beekes (2004); Simon (2015 13–14 and n. 61).

¹⁰³ Cf. Lane Fox (2009 351–352).

¹⁰⁴ Rieken, Sasseville, and Steer (2026).

¹⁰⁵ Monier-Williams (1899 504, 506); Mylius (2005 222). Cf. Pali word for “tooth”: “*duvijā* sind aber die ‘Zweimalgeborenen’, ein Ausdruck, der bei Zähnen nur die zweiten Zähne bedeuten kann” (Falk 1993 212).

¹⁰⁶ Cf. Knapp (1974 214).

¹⁰⁷ Cf. Hoffner (1974 108–109, 198; 1997 99, § 101/*1; 198); HEG A-K 460, s.v. *gaga-*; HED K 14-15 s.v. *kaka-*; EDHIL 427-428, s.v. *kaka-*.

From this tentative analysis, the etymology of the widely discussed PN Κανθαύλης — found in Lydia¹⁰⁸ and Lycia,¹⁰⁹ and as Καθαυλις in Pisidia¹¹⁰ — may be clarified through the segmentation **ka-*, “offspring” + **-tawal-*, thus meaning “royal kin.”¹¹¹ This interpretation contradicts what is commonly maintained about *kandaules* (Högemann and Oettinger 2018 38):

Kandaules, der letzte Heraklide auf dem Thron, hieß nach Herodot (1,7,2) mit wirklichem Namen Myrsilos. Nach Nikolaos von Damaskos hieß er dagegen Sadyattes, ein Name, den Herodot nur dem Vorgänger des Alyattes aus dem Geschlecht der Mermnaden zuweist. Kandaules ist jedenfalls in Wirklichkeit ein lydisches Apellativum der Bedeutung ‘Anführer, Herrscher’ (s. Teil 4).

As recently noted by Melchert (2024 240) regarding CLuw. *tāwana/i-* “upright, erect” and Hitt. *tawana-*, the “noun *dawani-* ‘spine, stalk’” is derived from the latter.¹¹² It is noteworthy that it appears with *kaki-* in a passage of CTH 480.1, which Mouton (2010 112) translates as follows: “maintenant je viens de peler cet oignon. Je n’ai gardé de lui qu’une tige (et) un morceau (insignifiant).”¹¹³ Although *šuppiwašhar* is generally translated as “onion” rather than “garlic,”¹¹⁴ as suggested by H. Hoffner, what remains after peeling is a clove, and in any case, the botanical metaphor is compelling.

Perhaps, a reference to *tabalātum* (< *tawal-*)¹¹⁵ — an Anatolian loanword in Akkadian Texts from Kültepe (Dercksen 2007 37) — can give a useful insight (Alp 1997 43):¹¹⁶

Zu den im altassyrischen Material vorkommenden hethitischen Wörtern gehören auch die in den hethitischen Festrivalen oft belegten Getränke *marnuan* und *tawal*, die Biersorten darstellen. Sie erscheinen in den altassyrischen Texten von Kappadokien als *marnuatum* und *tabalatum*.

¹⁰⁸ KPN 213, § 521: “Name aus der sagenhaften Genealogie d. lyd. Königen (Hdt. 1, 8 sqq.); richtig als illyrisch gedeutet von Masson, *Kratylos* 2, 1957, 64 (mit der älteren Literatur).” Cf. LGPN-Ling, *Kandaulēs*, [https://lgpn-ling.huma-num.fr/Kandaulēs]; Smith (1920); Robertson (1982 135–139); Evans (1985); Spina (1999); Pisano (2011b; 2011a 256ff.); Bonati (2013 40, 46); S. Hawkins (2013 167–182); Bettarini (2017 27–34); Högemann and Oettinger (2018 28–37, 69–71); Garnier and Sagot (2020 179); Posani (2023).

¹⁰⁹ LGPN VB 227.

¹¹⁰ LGPN VC 203.

¹¹¹ Högemann and Oettinger (2018 6–7): “Nicht gering zu achten sind allerdings die lydischen Wörter in griechischer Nebenüberlieferung, wie etwa die ‘lydischen’ Königstitel, *kandaules* und schließlich *tyrannos* (s. Glossar), das eine kompliziertere Vorgeschichte aufweist.”

¹¹² Melchert (1999 367; 2014b 261): “Likewise Hittite attests *dawani-* anim. ‘stem, stalk’ (*‘the straight thing’) ← *tawana-* ‘straight; true.’” Cf. Bauer, Yakubovich, and Sasseville (2026).

¹¹³ Cf. HEG A-K 462 where *kaki-* is treated as an adjective and translated as “*kahl*, *armselig*, *dünn*” and HFR-Team, hethiter.net/: HFR-Glossare (2022-01-12). Goetze (1947 319): “In the course of the ritual the magician subjects the plant to the destructive action *šippa-*; as a result he is able to state: ‘Now I have only one *kakin dawandin* left’, conceivably (hapax legomena can naturally only be guessed at) ‘(only) one miserable stem’ or the like.” René. Lebrun (1976 131) translates the passage as follows: “Maintenant voici que j’ai pelé complètement l’oi[gn]on; j’[en] ai conservé seulement un tige nue.” Puhvel (1992 265): “In one such episode (Rs. 36 — 41) she is handed an onion which she describes as wrapped in its skin in such a way that one layer does not let go of another. She then proceeds to peel the onion and ends up holding a mere *kākin dawandin*, hapax legomena of inferential meaning, perhaps ‘lousy stump’ or the like.” Torri (2003 142): “Ora ecco, questa cipolla (40-41) ho sbucciato e ne ho conservato un misero gambo.” J.L. Miller (2010 178 n. 37): “Now I myself have peeled this o[ni]on, [and] I have left one bare stem.” Görke and Melzer (2016): “Ich behielt dabei nur einen dünnen Stengel zurück” (§ 18).

¹¹⁴ Witczak (2006).

¹¹⁵ “*tawal-* gen. n. ‘(kultisches Getränk, eine Biersorte)’” [HFR-Team, hethiter.net/: HFR-Glossare (2022-01-12)]; HEG T 278-279; Rieken (1999 456, 495).

¹¹⁶ Einar von Schuler (1969 321–322). Cf. Hutter (1988 61): “Eventuell kann man auch für *tawal-* an eine Entlehnung aus einer nichtidg. Sprache Kleinasiens denken, wobei das in altassyrischen Texten bezugte *tabalātum* ebenfalls in diesem Zusammenhang genannt werden kann.” Schwemer (2005–2006 222); Puhvel (2011 103): “While *tawal*, like the similar brews *limma-* and *walhi-*, is etymologically opaque, they all like *marnuan*, apparently denoted local varieties of beers and ales.”

The Hittite *tawal-*,¹¹⁷ which denotes a top-quality beer¹¹⁸ served to the king¹¹⁹ and offered in libation to the gods,¹²⁰ might be equivalent to the logogram KAŠ.LUGAL¹²¹ attested at Alalah.¹²² This hypothesis is supported by the existence of a specific office, the ^{LU}*tawalala-*, who is the man in charge of the *tawal*-beverage.¹²³

5.2. A few insights into the semantics of **-ka-*

A promising approach to the onomastics involving **-ka-* is the toponym *Išmirika*,¹²⁴ which is clearly formed with Hittite *išmeri-*, “rein,” about which Güterbock (1957) has made decisive remarks, in his review of J. Friedrich’s *Hethitisches Wörterbuch* (1952):

Other entries require more comment. Some of my suggestions were caused by the feeling that one has to look for a logical link between seemingly disparate meanings. One of these was *išmeri-* and *išmeriyant-* (p. 88 f.): the “lords of the *išmeri-*”, obviously charioteers in the annals of Tudhaliya, and the animal *awiti* (lion or sphinx) which is described as *išmeriyant-* in a Bildbeschreibung (MVAG 46, 2, p. I4 ii 8) cannot be combined on the basis of a “Stellung” or “Gangart” (ibid. p. 32 n. 2) but only if *išmeri-* is a rein, the charioteers are “lords of the rein”, and the lion is “provided with a line or leash” as so frequently depicted. This proposal was later confirmed by Laroche, RHA 57, 8i ff., who adduced the decisive passage where *išmeri-* is written with the determinative KUŠ “leather” from a Geneva text which had escaped me. See now also his article on the hieroglyph for “charioteer”, which is a picture of reins, RHA 58, 29 ff. One may now safely read the well-known ŠA KUŠ . KA . TAB . ANŠU of Hatt. i 12 as *išmeriyaš* “(man) of the rein”.

The *išmeriyaš išha-* “‘Herr des (Pferde-)Halfters’ (ŠA KUŠKIR4.TAB.ANŠE)” (Cotticelli-Kurras 2016 87)¹²⁵ refers to a special role within the Hittite army¹²⁶ and suggests interpreting *Išmirika*¹²⁷ as the **ka-* of *išmeri-*, that is, “offspring/sons of the rein.” The same may apply to *Mastigga*,¹²⁸ this time a PN, but still a name related to Kizzuwatna, like *Išmirika*.¹²⁹

Given that the Lydian term *masta-* translates to “ornament” (Yakubovich 2026b) and appears in the western Anatolian toponym *Mastaura*,¹³⁰ it is probable that *Mastigga* originally designated a craft

¹¹⁷ Morphologically, *tawal-* may be compared with *suppal-*, “livestock.” Cf. HEG S 1179-1182; EDHIL 788; Watkins (1994); Rieken (1999 432).

¹¹⁸ HEG T 279: “dieses Getränk nicht nur den Göttern geopfert, sondern auch bei Hof getrunken wurde.”

¹¹⁹ Barsacchi (2017 78–79); Oğuz Soysal (2019 162, 165); Steitler (2020 323).

¹²⁰ Coşkun (1969 14); Ünal (1999 220); Czyzewska (2012 45); Arroyo (2020 22).

¹²¹ Veenhof (1972 203–205), in his comparative survey of Old Assyrian scale qualities, suggests moving beyond the literal sense of the logogram LUGAL when it follows several consumer goods: “Of course LUGAL originally meant that the item in question was for use by the king and his court: they received the finest products. This concrete meaning may have obtained, even when LUGAL had become an indication of quality; we cannot easily distinguish the two” (204).

¹²² Gaál (1972 288; 1982 17–18, 21, 23, 35).

¹²³ Pecchioli Daddi (1982 58, 60–61; 2004 465 and n. 104); Popko (2009 76); Mouton and Erbil (2020 49 n. 6).

¹²⁴ RGTC VI 149; RGTC VI/2 55.

¹²⁵ Pecchioli Daddi (1982 113–114); Beal (1992 153–154).

¹²⁶ Beal (1992 39).

¹²⁷ Houwink ten Cate (1970 5, 61, 63, 73); Kempinski and Košak (1970); Oettinger (1976 60, 78, 80–81, 93); Klengel (1998 118, 124); Freu (2001 26); Trameri (2024 76–77).

¹²⁸ NH 116, § 782; Haas (2006 113, 306).

¹²⁹ Trémouille (2001 68 n. 81): “À ce propos on doit souligner que l’existence même d’un accord conclus avec ces localités prouve que ni Ura ni Išmirikka ne faisaient partie du territoire de Kizzuwatna, tout en étant géographiquement proches et en participant du même système politique.” Cf. Beal (1992 41): “It thus appears that the Išmirikans were stationed in a number of cities of recently-annexed Kizzuwatna with duties that included the suppression of local disturbances.” Beal (1992 78–79): “The location of this district is completely unknown. The fact that the Išmirikans are mentioned in this text in conjunction with Kizzuwatna and Mittanni merely tells us where the Išmirikans were stationed, not the location of Išmirika.” Beal (1986 437 n. 66): “However, the signatories are called LÚ.MEŠ KUR ^{URU}Išmirika, ‘men of Išmirika.’ [...] this must mean that these people are ethnically Išmirikans. ‘In Kizzuwatna his city is GN’ probably indicates that when stationed in Kizzuwatna, they were in that city. [...] In fact only two of the names might be Hurrian, the remainder being Luwian.”

¹³⁰ KON 373-374, § 788; L. Robert (1980 325 and n. 16); Blümel (1998–2012 175); Hild (2004 122); Nollé (2016); Schürr (2016a).

guild. This follows a semantic pattern observed in certain Semitic languages, such as Hebrew,¹³¹ where the term for “son” functions as a marker for guild membership when paired with a specific profession.¹³² As duly observed by Frick (1971 282),

[...] *ben*, like the Akkadian terms *māru* and *aplu*, could mean that the person in question is a member of an occupational group or a guild. Guilds followed the model of the family system from which they had originated. The heads of such guilds were given the familial designation “father” while the apprentices were termed “sons.”

This may also hold true for *Kakarpa*,¹³³ if we assume **karpa-* as the Anatolian calque of the Akkadian *karpu* (“jar”).¹³⁴ Drawing a parallel with the Ugaritic *bn hrš* (“artisan”),¹³⁵ the toponym suggests a potters’ settlement,¹³⁶ consistent with a generic meaning of *-ka-* as “offspring.” This etymological framework likely extends to *Išmirika*, which can read as the “place where the men of the rein live.” As for *Kakarpa*, we only know that it belongs to a cluster of cities related to Kinnara. According to the only available source, Kinnara should be on the coast of the Black Sea (Forlanini 1977 218). This tentative localisation, accepted by Freu (1987 166), suggests for *Kakarpa* the Bithynian harbour *Karpē* (TIB XIII 647),¹³⁷ 50 km north-east of ancient Nikomedia. If the Hittite toponym is a compound formed by **ka-* “offspring” and **-karpa-* “jar,” it stands to reason that the latter can be found alone, as it seems to frequently occur in Anatolian place names (KON 226-228).

With appropriate caution due to the historical and geographical distance, the case of *Κακολεῖς*¹³⁸ (a PN from modern Kula in Lydia)¹³⁹ may support the previous insight about compounds formed with initial **ka-*. As modern Kula probably corresponds to **-kol-*,¹⁴⁰ the PN can be parsed as **ka-* (“offspring”) and *-koleis*, likely derived from the toponym itself. *Κακολεῖς* can be interpreted as a gentilic in *-eis*, and this is confirmed by its use as a *supernomen*; in the double name *Στρατόνεικος Κακολεῖς*, the latter may specify that he belongs to the people (“offspring”) of Kula (Ricl 2010 546). Such gentilics — Zgusta refers to them as “Einwohnernamen (abgekürzt EwN)” (KON 12)¹⁴¹ — are common throughout Anatolia, as shown by the following survey:

Akaliseis (Lycia, KON 52, § 30)
Alindeis (Caria, KON 62, § 44-11)
Areneis (Lydia, KON 85, § 85-1)
Ariasseis (Pisidia, KON 94 § 91-3)
Etenneis (Pamphylia, KON 174, § 310)
Themēseis (Caria, KON 183, § 339-1)
Thegeis (Lydia, KON 184, §)
Kabalēneis (Phrygia, KON 207, § 396)
Kaduēneis (Phrygia, KON 210, § 403-2)

Mylaseis (Caria, KON 406, § 861-1)
Oloandeis (Isauria, KON 436, § 930-1)
Orbaniteis (Galatia, KON 440, § 938-2)
Panamareis (Caria, KON 466, § 1000)
Pidaseis (Caria, KON 489, § 1054-1)
Plaraseis (Caria, KON 499, § 1071)
Plataseis (Caria, KON 500, § 1072)
Prieneis (Caria, KON 508, § 1100-1)
Sagalasseis (Pisidia, KON 522, § 1141)

¹³¹ Eckhardt (2019 10 n. 38): “Neh 3.8 for the use of *ben* to indicate belonging to a professional group.”

¹³² Schniedewind (2013 59). Cf. Mendelsohn (1940); Levine (1963 211); Astour (1964 245); Dothan (1985 84 n. 9); Vita Barra (2018); W.G.E. Watson (2018 348–349). West (1997 622–623) has applied this analogy with Phoenician professional names to explain “the imaginary ancestor of the Homeridai.”

¹³³ RGTC VI/1 162; J.L. Miller (2013b 199). *Kakarpa* belongs to the district of Kinnara, for which localisation, cf. Forlanini (1977 218); Freu (1987 166); Matthews and Glatz (2009 66–67); Forlanini (2013b 51); Barat (2013 152); De Martino (2017 256–258).

¹³⁴ AHW III 1566, CAD K 221. Cf. Huld and Mallory (1997 444), s.v. **kelp-* “jug, pot”: “It has been suggested that the IE word may derive from Semitic, e.g., Akkadian *karpu* ‘recipient’, but this seems very distant.”

¹³⁵ Olmo Lete and Sanmartín (2015 227, 371). Cf. Eckhardt (2019 9 n. 34): “the possible use of kinship terminology indicating membership, e.g. *KTU* 4.214 (*bn hrš* = “belonging to the craftsmen”).”

¹³⁶ Haag (1999 152): “*ben* and *bar* are also used to denote membership in certain social and professional groups. [...] The following expressions refer to professional groups: *ben haraqqachim*, ‘son of perfumers’ = perfumer (Neh. 3:8), and *bene hameshorerim*, singers {Neh. 12:28}.”

¹³⁷ {Foss, 2012 #19150@@author-year}. Cf. Munk Højte (2008 156–158); Aslan (2014).

¹³⁸ Cf. *Κολεῖς* (LGPV VC 225) in Cappadocian Komana.

¹³⁹ TAM V 1 246; Herrmann and Polatkan (1969 51–53); Ricl (1991 3); Mitchell (1970 63 n. 34); Chiaï (2009 61–63; 2020 32).

¹⁴⁰ KON 277, § 554. Cf. Lane (1975 105–108).

¹⁴¹ Cf. Vandorpe (2000 500); Guldager Bilde (2024 193).

Kanytēldeis/Kanytēlideis (Cilicia, KON 225, § 433)
Karseis (?) (Mysia, KON 232, § 453-2)
Kastanneis (Lycia, KON 238, § 459-1)
Kasōsseis (Caria, KON 240, § 461-4)
Katenneis (Pisidia, KON 240-241, § 462-1)
Kidyēsseis (Phrygia, KON 255, § 502)
Koarendeis/Kōranzeis (Caria, KON 273, § 538-2)
Lyrnanteis (Lycia, KON 348, § 732-1)
Lystreis (Lycaonia, KON 349, § 734)
Marmareis (Lycia, KON 369, § 774)
Moandeis (Cilicia, KON 390, § 821-1)
Moatreis (Pisidia, KON 390, § 821-2)

Saloudeis (Phrygia, KON 530, § 1151)
Sedaseis (Pisidia-Lycaonia, KON 550, § 1186-1)
Selgeis (Pisidia, KON 551, § 1187)
Tabaleis (Lydia, KON 594, § 1277-2)
Telmesseis (Lycia, KON 608, § 1314)
Termesseis (Pisidia, KON 613, § 1320-3)
Tigrosalleis (Pisidia, KON 620, § 1341)
Toilokaisareis (Lydia, KON 625, § 1351)
Kaisareis Trokettēnoi (Lydia, KON 635, § 1370)
Tymandeis (Pisidia, KON 639, § 1382)
Hyllarameis (Caria, KON 651, § 1404-2)
Hyrgaleis (Caria, KON 653, § 1409-1)
Hytenneis (Pamphylia, KON 174, 656, §§ 310, 1417)

The Hellenised male PN *Kakoleis*, which Zgusta defines as a “gentilic” (*Einwohnername*), can usefully be compared with *Katenneis*, which he considers an ethnonym (*Stammname*). What Hellenkemper and Hild (2004 614) state about *Katenneis*, one of the above toponyms, may help resolve some localisation problems and support the hypothesis developed in this section:

Katenneis (Κατεννεῖς), antike Volksgruppe im pisid.-pamphyl. Hochland, mit den *Poleis* → Etenna, → Kotenna u. Erymna (→ Orymna); im W trennten die Göl Dağları das Siedlungsgebiet der *Katenneis* von der *Chōra* von → Selgē.

The similarity between the ethnics *Katenneis*¹⁴² and *Etenneis*¹⁴³ can be explained if **ka-* means “offspring” and *υῖοί* or *ὄοί*, “sons” was used as a Greek adaptation of an Anatolian ethnonym or vice versa. In either case, they would be compounds of **-tenneis*, possibly derived from *Tennes*,¹⁴⁴ the local hero of Tenedos, an “Asian-Aeolic-speaking island lying north of Lesbos and opposite the Troad” (Woodard 2024 186).¹⁴⁵ Given that a Pamphylian Tenedos is also known,¹⁴⁶ and that an Aeolian colonisation has received scholarly consensus, it stands to reason that *Etenneis* comes first.

It seems that the sound changes involving the diphthong *oi* may account for the different denominations, which are likely to share the same origin. The suggestion by Brixhe (1987 48), according to which *υῖός* renders /ijos/, so that the plural *υῖοί* would be pronounced /ijoi/, cannot be taken at face value for *Etenneis*, as it refers to a later evolution of the diphthong *ui* in the koiné.¹⁴⁷ In fact, “the data from the inscriptions [...] show that by 350 BCE *ὄός* had become the normal spelling (Favi 2024 245).¹⁴⁸ Therefore, assuming a pronunciation close to /i:/ would not account for the earliest numismatic attestation of the toponym *Etenna*, which dates to the fourth century. If, at the time of the first occurrence of *Etenna*, the plural Attic form is *ὄοί* and *oi* is monophthongised to /y/,¹⁴⁹ we should thus suppose that it is likely pronounced /y:/, given that this assumption could also apply to another ethnic, Ὑτεννέων, which some scholars consider refers to the same population (Sekunda 1996 14).¹⁵⁰

¹⁴² Foss et al. (2024).

¹⁴³ TIB VIII 531-533; Arena (2005 189–190); Foss et al. (2017). Cf. Bean (1970); Nollé (1984, 1992); Çevik (2003).

¹⁴⁴ *Cypria* 9 (West 2003 75–77). Cf. Leaf (1923 214–222); Brelich (2010 134–135); Specht (2001); Killen (2008); Kisbali (2020).

¹⁴⁵ Cf. Napolitano (2005).

¹⁴⁶ Arena (2005 146); Adak (2006); Brixhe (2013 199–200, 202); Asinmaz and Özcan (2023); Fatih (2023); Tüner Önen and Arslan (2025).

¹⁴⁷ Karvounis (2008 61): “Die Monophthongierung von *ui* gilt für das 5. und 4. Jh. (im Attischen) als gesichert; fraglich ist nur, ob *υ* den Lautwert [y] oder [i] besaß bzw. beide.”

¹⁴⁸ From Threatte (1980–1996 I 340), we learn that for *υῖός*, “after 450 B.C. retention of the iota is rare in any form of this word” and that “in the period ca. 450-ca.100 B.C.” it rarely occurs. Cf. Threatte (1980–1996 II 220–222).

¹⁴⁹ Brixhe (2010 232): “/oi/ has evolved toward /y/ and hence OI became over time another graphemic representation of /i/.” Cf. Lejeune (1972 231); Karvounis (2008 59–60); D.G. Miller (2013a 53–54); Julián Méndez Dosuna (2021 126 and n. 35). For the Pamphylian dialect, Brixhe (1976 36) and for the Anatolian Greek, Brixhe (1987 50).

¹⁵⁰ KON 656, § 1417; TIB VIII 563; Toynbee (1910). Cf. Asheri, Lloyd, and Corcella (2007 483): “[...] however, it is the Ἐτεννεῖς, who in the Hellenistic age are known in this area: cf. Walbank 1, pp. 599-600. They are probably a mountain tribe, with a town called Etenna in Pisidia; cf. Müller 11, pp. 262-6.”

Settlement spread to the more remote areas of Pisidia only in the late Hellenistic period, but political and social organization seems to have continued to be ‘cantonal’ in nature for some time. One of these tribal groupings was called the Hytenneis, whom Herodotus (3.90) mentions as belonging to the second nomos established by the Persian King Darius for the gathering of tribute, together with the Mysians, Lydians, Lasonians and Cabalians. The Hytenneis seem to be the tribal grouping who eventually established the cities of Etenna, Kotenna and Erymna (and perhaps others) which all lie in the Melas river valley system to the north of the Pamphylian city of Side.

If the solution proposed by Julian Méndez Dosuna (1988) regarding the evolution of the diphthong /oi/ in Boiotia, which he summarises as follows (Mendez Dosuna 2008 327), can be applied to *Etenna*, we could explain the initial *e-* as the graphemic rendition of /ø:/,¹⁵¹ that is, the likely pronunciation of *ὄοί*, “sons”:

[oi.] (<OI>) > [oɛ] (<OE>) > [ø:] (<Y>) > [e:] (<EI>)

A similar oscillation between initial *o-* and *e-* is attested in Pamphylia with the toponym Ὀροῦνα (KON 442, § 952-1), which also occurs as Ἐροῦνα.¹⁵² Of course, the case of the three Pamphylian toponyms cannot be decisive in proving that *ka-* is a nominal form with the precise meaning “offspring,” but further indications in this direction can be found in Anatolian onomastics. This first millennium evidence should be considered together with second millennium GNN such as *Serikka*, a theophoric name,¹⁵³ and an occupational PN such as *Mastigga*,¹⁵⁴ according to what I tentatively argued in this section.

We may have further confirmation with the Hittite GN *Gawattaru*,¹⁵⁵ provided we parse it as *Ga-* + *-wattaru*, the latter being a variant of the GN *Wattarwa*.¹⁵⁶ The same can be assumed for *Kakumaḫa*,¹⁵⁷ i.e. **Ka-* + *-kumaḫa*, in which the latter corresponds to the GN *Kummaḫa*.¹⁵⁸

5.3. *neka-, nekna-, kaina-, a reconsideration*

Evidence from Anatolian onomastics invites a re-evaluation of well-known Hittite terms of uncertain etymology. From this analysis, a clearer understanding of the proposed meaning for Hittite *ka-* may finally emerge:

- 1 *neka-*, “sister” (EDHIL 601),¹⁵⁹ already attested as *-nika-* in the PNN from Kültepe (EDHIL 756);
- 2 *nekna-* (EDHIL 602) or *-nikna-* as resulting from *pappan(n)ikna-*,¹⁶⁰ “brother sharing the same father, paternal brother” (EDHIL 627);
- 3 *kaina-*, “brother in-law” (EDHIL 427).

¹⁵¹ Brixhe (1987 50): “la monophthongaison de */oi/ en tout positions, sans doute réalisé [ø] par la majorité des locuteurs attiques dès le milieu du IV^e siècle a.C.” Cf. Bernard and Bopearachchi (2002 250): “le remplacement de oi par o marquerait un étape dans ce processus de monophthongaison, la graphie o pouvant noter un son o prononcé comme «peu.»”

¹⁵² TIB VIII 769-770; (Foss et al. 2012); Brixhe (1976 20; 1991 72–73; 1996 83).

¹⁵³ Cf. the GN *Kapanuwanta*, transparently composed by **Ka-* and the theonym *Panuwanta-/Panunta-* (Hutter 1988 86, 89, 108, 110–111, 123, 131, 166; Mouton 2015 83–84; Marcuson 2016 218, 220–221, 288). The PN *Karruwa* (NH 88, §533) is probably formed by *Ruwa*, a known avatar of the theonym *Runta*. Cf. de Martino (1983 308). To the latter family of names may also belong the Lydian PN *Karos* (KPN 217, § 542; LW I 44, 58, 70, 144; II 63–64). Cf. Meriggi (1935 89–90); Zgusta (1955 522–524); Gusmani (1975 139; 1979 78); Kearns (1994 10–11); Schürr (2006 1571).

¹⁵⁴ Cf. *Salikka*, whose title is GAL UKU.UŠ, that is “capo degli armati pesanti” (Pecchioli Daddi 1982 546). Cf. Rosi (1984 123–125); (Beal 1992 380–391; Van den Hout 1995 167–168); Imparati (2004 328–329, 512); Bilgin (2018 222, 228–230, 394). Considering that CLuw. *šāla-* means “(a type of harness), leather strap” (Rieken 2026b) and his role in the royal army, his name may be occupational. Cf. Melchert (2024 198). The Hebrew *šālīš* may serve as term of comparison (Mastin 1979; Noonan 2019 355–356).

¹⁵⁵ RGTC VI/2 77, s.v. *Kawataru*. Cf. Süel and Weeden (2017 205).

¹⁵⁶ RGTC VI/1 481–482, s.v. *Watarwa*.

¹⁵⁷ RGTC VI/2 59–60.

¹⁵⁸ RGTC VI/1 220–221 and RGTC VI/2 83.

¹⁵⁹ CHD L-N 425ff.

¹⁶⁰ Hoffner (1988 194–197).

By parsing the first two terms, we identify a shared morphological feature: the negative particle /*ne-*,¹⁶¹ as in the HLuw. nouns /*niwarann(i)-*-, “child” (Bauer 2025) and /*nimuwizza-*-, “son” (Bauer 2025). Furthermore, this approach offers a twofold advantage: it aligns with the latest view on these kinship terms and avoids the pitfalls of Neumann’s theory (1991) as identified by Melchert (2012b 214 n. 16), who points to Luvian *nāna/i-* and Lycian *nēne/i-* (both meaning “brother”) as counterevidence.¹⁶²

Unfortunately, the very attractive etymology of Neumann (1991: 63-4), **ni-ngh₁-ó* ‘inborn’, runs afoul of the already OS spelling *ne-eg-na* in KBo 20.31 Ro 6, whose *e*-vocalism cannot be derived from **ni-*. The Luvian and Lycian obviously also exclude **ni-*, if they are in fact cognate!

If *kaina-* (“brother-in-law”) is segmented as **ka-* + **-e/ina*, a new morphological path opens for **nekna-*. In light of the Proto-Anatolian negative particle **ne* (Payne, Bauer, Sasseville, et al. 2026),¹⁶³ *nekna-* and *neka-* appear to share a common **ka-* component. Under this view, *nekna-* represents a derivative of **nek(ae)na-*¹⁶⁴ following the syncope of its post-tonic vowel.¹⁶⁵

As argued above, following a lead from HLuw. /*nimuwizza-*-, “son” and /*niwarann(i)-*-, “child,” where *ni-* is a privative morpheme,¹⁶⁶ *nekna-* < **ne-* + **-kna-* (< *kaina-*) would literally mean “non-brother in-law,” i.e. “blood brother.” This may recall the distinction between the Latin *frater* and *frater germanus*,¹⁶⁷ and even suggest a possible etymology of **ka-* as derived from PIE **ǵeǵH-* (LIV² 161), “aufbrechen, keimen” (IEW 355-6).¹⁶⁸

Now, if we segment *kaina-* as **ka-* + **-e/ina-*,¹⁶⁹ and allow a reassessment of the common view of both the morphology and semantics of this term, we can focus on its first element and interpret it as “male child.” The addition of the putative suffix **-ena* could suggest a comparison with the Latin *filiaster*, “brother in-law,”¹⁷⁰ and justify an interpretation as “stepson” or “half-son.”

Following Bammesberger (2004 94),¹⁷¹ we could assume that the Hittite **ka-* reflects an *o*-grade formation of PIE **ǵeǵH-*. If **ka-* denotes the “sprouted,”¹⁷² i.e. “blood” son, then **ka-e/ina* would mean a male child who is less than that, assigning to the suffix *-ena/-ina* (Pozza 2023) a function also

¹⁶¹ Melchert (1987 201; 1990 204); Rieken (2003 43–44); Payne, Bauer, Sasseville, et al. (2026).

¹⁶² Cf. Billing, Sasseville, and Höfler (2026).

¹⁶³ Cf. Davies (1975).

¹⁶⁴ EDHIL 100, 427; Kimball (1994 17–22).

¹⁶⁵ Evidence of syncope of the post-tonic vowel, that is, the loss of the medial vowel following the stressed one, comes from *titnu-* < *tittanu-* (Melchert 2018 30). Cf. René Lebrun (1981 119): “*ti-it-nu-ut*: forme réduite de *tittanut*.” Contra EDHIL 884: “Although this verb is predominantly spelled *ti-it-ta-nu-*, we find spellings with *ti-it-nu-* as well (from OH/MS onwards), which point to a phonological interpretation /*titnu-*.”

¹⁶⁶ Starke (1990 452–453); Dunkel (2014 559).

¹⁶⁷ Benveniste (1969 I, 213, 221); Hackstein (2024 3–4). Cf. Tukey (1962 32): “Classic Latin *germanus*, *germana* was an adjective meaning ‘sprouted’ in general usage, or ‘own, full-blooded, related’ in the kinship framework.” The Greek ἀδελφός, “brother,” presents an analogous case (Teppa 2013).

¹⁶⁸ Cf. Knapp (1974 214).

¹⁶⁹ Rieken (2019 219–221) raises doubts about the usual interpretation of Hitt. *kaina-* as derived from **koi-no*. Cf. Kloekhorst (2010 220): “The etymology of this word is difficult. The fluctuation between spellings with *-i-* and *-e-* is highly remarkable and unexplained. When compared to a word like *pa-i-mi* = /*páimi*/ ‘I go’, which is never spelled **pa-e-mi*, it seems that *ga-i-na-/ga-e-na-* cannot be simply interpreted as /*gaina-*/. Therefore Hrozný’s proposal (1919, 100–1) to connect *gaina-/gaena-* to Lat. *civis* ‘citizen’, Skt. *śiva-* ‘friendly’, which implies a reconstruction **koi-no-* and nowadays seems to be quite generally accepted, cannot be correct.”

¹⁷⁰ Cf. Thomas (1940); Rybolt (1971); P. Watson (1989).

¹⁷¹ “If we follow up this line of reasoning, then it is thinkable that Gmc. **kajj-* is related to a root (zero-grade) **kī-*. A root **kī-* may be recognized in several formations, e.g. GO. *keinan* ‘sprout’ (< **kī-n-*); without suffixal *-n-* the root **kī-* is found in the Gothic past participle *us-kijanata* ‘φρέν’ (Luke 8.6).” Bammesberger (2004 97 n. 24) further notes that “Pokorny 1959:355) posits the Indo-European root as **ǵēi/ǵī-*, the long-vowel alternant **ǵī-* may be recognized in Lithuanian *zydėti* ‘blossom’. Rix (1998:142) gives the root as **geyH-* ‘aufbrechen, keimen’. A thematic *o*-grade formation **goyH-o-* could be expected in Germanic as **kaj-a-* or possibly **kajj-a-*.” Cf. Holthausen (1912 48).

¹⁷² Cf. Greek ὄζος, “bough, branch, twig,” and “metaph., offshoot, scion” (LSJ).

seen in the Hittite *lappina-*, likely derived from the verb *lapp-*, “glow,”¹⁷³ and probably meaning “burning like fire,”¹⁷⁴ as Latin *urtica* relates to *uro*.¹⁷⁵

In the case of the Hittite *kaina-*, we can use Magni’s remark about the Latin suffix *-inus* (2017 290):

[...] the suffix itself finds new functions, starting to develop evaluative meanings in substandard formations. [...] As a matter of fact, many languages offer examples of similar polysemies, and many affixes develop evaluative functions through semantic change from primary possessive and relational meanings. [...] In this view, various sources of diminutive suffixes, and *-inus* as well, can thus be interpreted as “proprietary markers” that link a possessum and a possessor according to a wide range of relations.

We can observe that the Hittite *-ena* — basically a possessive suffix — may, in the case of *kaena-*, have the same diminutive function as the suffix *-anna/i*,¹⁷⁶ so that a meaning such as “little son” could correspond to “the Slavic use of the expression ‘little son’ for the brother’s son (e.g. Serbo-Croatian *sinovac*: see Buck 1949:11)” (Gates 1971 55).¹⁷⁷ The analogy with this word or with “Fr. *petit-fils* (13th cent.), lit. ‘little son’” (Buck 1988 112) is not conclusive, but it is noteworthy that Indo-European languages use diminutives such as Lat. *avunculus*¹⁷⁸ or add “little” to define kinship relationships on the wife’s side.

As for *nika-*, “sister,” based on the proposal above, it can be parsed as *ni-* + *-ka-*, and if the latter possibly means “offspring, son, male child,” then “sister” would be referred to as a “non-male child.”¹⁷⁹ This meaning is reflected in HLuw. *nanasri-*,¹⁸⁰ where the suffix *-(a)šr(i)-*,¹⁸¹ used to mark female names, is added to *nana-* “brother.”

Abbreviations

ACLT = Annotated Corpus of Luwian Texts.
 AHw = Von Soden (1959–1981).
 AIO = Attic Inscriptions Online.
 AJPh = The American Journal of Philology.
 AJA = American Journal of Archaeology.
 AnSt = Anatolian Studies.
 AoF = Altorientalische Forschungen.
 AP = Zgusta (1964a).
 ArchOrient = Archív Orientální.
 BATL = Talbert (2000).

BCH = Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique.
 BoHa 19 = Herbordt (2005).
 BoHa 22 = Dinçol and Dinçol (2008).
 CAD = Roth et al. (1956–2010).
 CHLI = J.D. Hawkins (2000).
 CIL = Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum.
 CLL = Melchert (2001).
 CLuw = Cuneiform Luwian.
 CMRDM = Lane (1971–1978).
 CP = Classical Philology.

¹⁷³ Cf. CHD L-N 38, 45; EDHIL 519; HED V 58-60; Carruba (1980 362); Stefanini (1983); Hoffner (2003 622); Melchert (2024 133).

¹⁷⁴ Cf. Vitti (1984); Stivala (2004 51–52); Francia (2019 132; 2020 137–139).

¹⁷⁵ De Vaan (2008 645).

¹⁷⁶ Sasseville (2026), s.v. *armann(i)-*: “Indeed, the suffix *-ann(i)-*, if from **-é-no-* (with Čop’s Law, see Sasseville 2017a:136), surely matches the Hittite adjectival suffix *-ēna-* (contra Melchert 2002e:297) and thus betrays the Luwian origin of the noun.” Cf. Sasseville and Höfler (2026): “If *-ann(i)-* is only Luwian, a pre-form **-é-no-*, matching the Hittite suffix *-ena-*, can be suggested (cf. Čop 1955d:400 “**-eni-*”), although a larger analysis of all the data is still missing.”

¹⁷⁷ Beekes (1976 54): “Compare Serb. *sinovac* ‘BrSo’, literally ‘kind of son’,” and Mallory and Adams (1997 393): “SC *sinóvac* ~ *sinôvac* ‘brother’s son’ (< *‘little son’).” Cf. Friedrich (1963 11): “In the second place, the highly descriptive nepotic terminology of Old Russian partly reflects a carry-over from Proto-Slavic (Chart 4), which used derivations from the brother term for the fraternal nepotes; *synovichl* [*synovičl*] the brother’s son, for example is morphologically ‘little son,’ and thereby implies that the (male) speaker is identifying with his own brothers, as would be natural in a patrilocal family.”

¹⁷⁸ Sesoldi (2019 133, 138–139); Bauer et al. (2024): “According to Schaffner 2005a:270–273, Lat. *avunculus* m. ‘uncle (mother’s brother)’, originally a diminutive formation meaning *‘little grandfather’, presupposes a derivational base **auon-* ‘grandfather’. [...] For the derivation Lat. **auon-* → *avun-culus*, cf., e.g., Lat. *homō*, *homin-is* ‘human being’ → *homun-culus* ‘homunculus’.”

¹⁷⁹ Cf. Armenian *aljik*.

¹⁸⁰ Cf. Cluw, *nānašri(ya)-* (Rieken 2026a).

¹⁸¹ Sasseville and Steer (2026).

- DBMAP = Mapping Ancient Polytheisms Database.
 DGE = Adrados (1980–).
 DGP = Brixhe (1976).
 DLL = Melchert (2004).
 EA = Epigraphica Anatolica.
 eDCo = eDiAna Corpora
 [https://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/corpus.php].
 EDHIL = Kloekhorst (2008a).
 EDPC 2 = Niehr and Xella (2021).
 EGEF = Tsagalis (2017).
 FEW = von Wartburg (1934).
 GD = Godefroy (1901).
 GLyk = Neumann and Tischler (2007).
 HED = Puhvel (1984–).
 HEG = Tischler (1977–2016).
 HF = Zehnder (2010).
 HLuw = Hieroglyphic Luwian.
 HKM = Alp (1991).
 LAMAN = https://laman.hittites.org/
 IACP = M.H. Hansen and Nielsen (2004).
 ICilicie = Dagron and Feissel (1987).
 IF = Indogermanische Forschungen.
 IDidyma = Harder (1958).
 IKibyra = Corsten (2002).
 IKibyra-Olbasa = Milner (1998).
 IManisa = Malay (1994).
 ISelge = Nollé and Schindler (1991).
 ISultan Dağı I = Jonnes (2002).
 IStratonikeia = Şahin (1981).
 JAOS = Journal of the American Oriental Society.
 JCS = Journal of Cuneiform Studies.
 JEOL = Jaarbericht van het Vooraziatisch-Egyptisch Genootschap Ex Oriente Lux.
 JHS = The Journal of Hellenic Studies.
 KAI³ = Donner and Röllig (1971–1976).
 KAI = Donner and Röllig (2002).
 KON = Zgusta (1984).
 KPN = Zgusta (1964b).
 LfgrE = Snell (1955–2010).
 LGPN VA = Corsten, Catling, and Riel (2010).
 LGPN VB = Balzat et al. (2013).
 LGPN VC = Balzat et al. (2018).
 LIV² = Rix et al. (2001).
 LPG = Houwink ten Cate (1961).
 LSJ = Liddell and Scott (1996).
 LW I = Gusmani (1964).
 LW II = Gusmani (1980).
 MAMA IV = Buckler, Calder, and Guthrie (1933).
 MAMA VI = Buckler and Calder (1939).
 MAMA VII = Calder (1956).
 MAMA VIII = Calder et al. (1962).
 MAMA X = Levick et al. (1993).
 MAMA XI = Thonemann, Crowther, and Chiricat (2013).
 McCabe = McCabe (1991).
 MGS = Montanari (2015).
 NABU = Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires.
 NH = Laroche (1966).
 NI = L. Robert (1963).
 NLH = News from the Lands of the Hittites.
 NP = Melchert (2013).
 Pleiades = *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places* [https://pleiades.stoa.org].
 RA = Revue archéologique.
 RÉA = Revue des Études Anciennes.
 RÉG = Revue des études grecques.
 RGTC VI = del Monte and Tischler (1978).
 RGTC VII/1 = Bagg (2008).
 RGTC VIII = Zadok (1985).
 RHA = Revue Hittite et Asianique.
 RIMA 3 = Grayson (1996).
 SB = Billerbeck (2006).
 SEG = Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum.
 SERP = Ramsay (1906).
 SMEA = Studi micenei ed egeo-anatolici.
 SNG = Ritter (1964).
 SNG Arikantürk = Tekin and Erol-Özdizbay (2015–2020).
 StBoTB 4 = Rüster and Wilhelm (2012).
 TAM II = Kalinka (1920–1944).
 TAM III = Heberdey (1941).
 TAM V 1 = Herrmann and Schachermeyr (1981).
 TAM V 3 = Petzl (2007).
 TIB II = Hild and Restle (1981).
 TIB IV = Belke and Restle (1984).
 TIB V = Hild and Hellenkemper (1990).
 TIB VII = Belke and Mersich (1990).
 TIB XIII = Belke (2020).
 T-L = Tobler (1857–2002).
 TL = Kalinka (1901).
 TLL = Thesaurus linguae Latinae.
 TP = Tabula Peutingeriana.
 ZA = Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und vorderasiatische Archäologie.
 ZPE = Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.

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Bibliography

- Adak, Mustafa. 2006. "Olbia in Pamphylien-Die epigraphische Evidenz." *Gephyra* 3: 1–28.
 ---. 2013. "Names, Ethnicity and Acculturation in the Pamphylian/Lycian Borderland." In *Personal Names in Ancient Anatolia*, edited by Robert Parker, 63–78. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
 Adiego, Ignasi-Xavier. 2007. *The Carian Language*. Leiden: Brill.
 ---. 2022. "Luwian *Tarhunaza-*, Cilician *Трокoвaζαs, Τρικoνaζαs*." *Indogermanische Forschungen* 127 (1): 75–90.
 Adrados, Francisco R., ed. 1980–. *Diccionario Griego-Español*. Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas.

- Alp, Sedat. 1991. *Masat-Höyük'te bulunan çivi yazılı Hitit tabletleri / Hethitische Keilschrifttafeln aus Masat-Höyük*. Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu Basımevi.
- . 1997. "Die Mehrheit der einheimischen Bevölkerung in der Karum-Zeit in Kanes/Nesa." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-anatolici* 39 (1): 35–48.
- Archi, Alfonso. 1966. "Trono regale e trono divinizzato nell'Anatolia ittita." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 1: 76–120.
- . 1975. "Il culto del focolare presso gli Ittiti." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 16: 77–87.
- . 1990. "The Names of the Primeval Gods." *Orientalia* 59 (2): 114–129.
- . 1993. "How a Pantheon Forms: The Cases of Hattian-Hittite Anatolia and Ebla of the 3rd Millennium BC." In *Religionsgeschichtliche Beziehungen zwischen Kleinasien, Nordsyrien und dem Alten Testament. Internationales Symposium Hamburg 17.-21. März 1990*, edited by Bernd Janowski, Klaus Koch and Gernot Wilhelm, 1–18. Freiburg-Göttingen: Universitätsverlag-Vandenhoeck Ruprecht.
- . 2002. "Formation of the West Hurrian Pantheon: The Case of Išhara." In *Recent Developments in Hittite Archaeology and History. Papers in Memory of Hans G. Güterbock*, edited by K. Aslihan Yener and A. Hoffner Harry, Jr., 21–34. University Park, USA: Penn State University Press.
- Arena, Gaetano. 2005. *Città di Panfilia e Pisidia sotto il dominio romano. Continuità strutturali e cambiamenti funzionali*. Catania: Edizioni del Prisma.
- Arroyo, Ana. 2014. "El agua dulce en la cultura hitita." Doctorado Europeo, Madrid: Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.
- . 2020. "Hittite Open-Air Cult Places and their Relation to the Community During Festivals." In *Ceremonies, Feasts and Festivities in Ancient Mesopotamia and the Mediterranean World. Performance and Participation. Proceedings of the 11th Melammu Workshop, Barcelona, 29–31 January 2020*, edited by Rocío Da Riva, Ana Arroyo and Céline Debourse, 13–50. Wien: Zaphon.
- Asheri, David, Alan B. Lloyd, and Aldo Corcella. 2007. *A Commentary on Herodotus*. Edited by Oswyn Murray and Alfonso
- Brosius Moreno, Maria. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Asinmaz, Alper, and Ertan Özcan. 2023. "Pamphylian Countryside: An Overview and a Gis-Based Spatial Investigation of Regional Settlement Patterns." *Scientific Culture* 9 (1): 107–132. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7459990>.
- Aslan, Erdoğan. 2014. "Bithynia Bölgesi Kalpe Limanı." *Olba* (22): 117–154.
- Astour, Michael C. 1964. "Second Millennium B. C. Cypriot and Cretan Onomastica Reconsidered." *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 84 (3): 240–254.
- Bagg, Ariel M. 2008. *Die Orts- und Gewässernamen der neuassyrischen Zeit. Teil 1: Die Levante*. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- Baglioni, Igor. 2017. *Echidna e i suoi discendenti. Studio sulle entità mostruose della Teogonia esiodea*. Roma: Edizioni Quasar.
- Balatti, Silvia. 2012. "Some Remarks on the Dating of the ANDAVAL Stela: Palaeographic and Iconographic Analysis." *Anatolica* 38: 149–168.
- Balzat, Jean-Sébastien. 2014. "Names in EPM-in Southern Asia Minor. A Contribution to the Cultural History of Ancient Lycia." *Chiron* 44: 253–284.
- Balzat, Jean-Sébastien, R. W. V. Catling, E. Chiricat, and Thomas Corsten, eds. 2018. *A Lexicon of Greek Personal Names. Volume V.C. Inland Asia Minor*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Balzat, Jean-Sébastien, R. W. V. Catling, E. Chiricat, James W. Marchand, and Thomas Corsten, eds. 2013. *A Lexicon of Greek Personal Names. Volume V.B. Coastal Asia Minor: Caria to Cilicia*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bammesberger, Alfred. 2004. "Old English *cæg* 'Key' And Frisian *kei / kai*." *North-Western Language Evolution* 44 (1): 91–100.
- Barat, Claire. 2013. "La Paphlagonie: histoire et peuplement." In *L'Anatolie des peuples, des cités et des cultures (IIe millénaire av. J.-C.-Ve siècle ap. J.-C.). Colloque international de Besançon 26-27 novembre 2010. Volume I. Autour d'un projet d'atlas historique et archéologique de l'Asie Mineure. Méthodologie et prospective*, edited by Hadrien Bru and Guy Labarre, 151–166. Besançon: Presses Universitaires de Franche-Comté.
- Barsacchi, Francesco G. 2017. *Le feste ittite del Tuono. Edizione critica di CTH 631*. Firenze: University of Firenze Press.
- Bauer, Anna. 2025. Hieroglyphic Luwian /*niwarann(i)-*, (INFANS)*ni-wa/i+ra/i-ni-* (eDiAna-ID 1389). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1389> (accessed 22/09/2025).
- Bauer, Anna, Susanne Görke, Jürgen Lorenz, and Elisabeth Rieken. 2014. "Mythologische Texte in hethitischer Sprache." In *Weisheitstexte, Mythen und Epen*, edited by Janowski Bernd and Schwemer Daniel, 145–176. Gütersloh: Gütersloher Verlagshaus.
- Bauer, Anna, Elisabeth Rieken, David Sasseville, Zsolt Simon, Carolin Schneider, and Thomas Steer. 2024. Proto-Anatolian **Héyh-eh2-/*HuH-éh2-* (eDiAna-ID 1500). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1500> (accessed 27/03/2024).
- Bauer, Anna, Zsolt Simon, David Sasseville, Elisabeth Rieken, Carolin Schneider, and Thomas Steer. 2022. Proto-Anatolian **uÉlgu-* (eDiAna-ID 1592). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1592> (accessed 20/04/2024).

- Bauer, Anna, Ilya Yakubovich, and David Sasseville. 2026. Common Luwian /*tawan(i)-*/ (eDiAna-ID 1404). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1404> (accessed 20/01/2026).
- Bawanyeck, Daliah. 2016. Das Ritual des Auguren H̱uwarlu (CTH 398). *hethiter.net/*: CTH 398 (INTR 2016-03-31). https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/intro.php?xst=CTH%20398&prgr=&lg=DE&ed=D.%20Bawanyeck.
- Beal, Richard H. 1986. "The History of Kizzuwatna and the Date of the Šunaššura Treaty." *Orientalia* 55 (4): 424–445.
- . 1992. *The Organisation of the Hittite Military*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- Bean, George E. 1970. "The site of Etenna." *Klio* 52 (52): 13–16.
- . 1971. *Journeys in Northern Lycia 1965-1967*. Wien: Böhlau.
- Beckman, Gary. 2004. "Pantheon. A. II. Bei den Hethitern." In *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*, edited by E. Ebeling and B. Meissner, 308–316. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Beekes, Robert. 1976. "Uncle and Nephew." *Journal of Indo-European Studies* 4 (1): 43–62.
- . 2004. "The Origin of the Kabeiroi." *Mnemosyne* 57 (4): 465–477.
- Beekes, Robert, and Lucien van Beek. 2010. *Etymological Dictionary of Greek*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Belke, Klaus. 2020. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 13. Bithynien und Hellespont*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Belke, Klaus, and Norbert Mersich. 1990. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 7. Phrygien und Pisidien*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Belke, Klaus, and Marcell Restle. 1984. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 4. Galatien und Lykaonien*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Benveniste, Émile. 1932a. "Le sens du mot κολοσσός et les noms grecs de la statue." *Revue de philologie, de littérature et d'histoire anciennes* 6: 118–135.
- . 1932b. "A propos de κολοσσός." *Revue de Philologie, de Littérature et d'Histoire Anciennes* 6: 381.
- . 1969. *Le vocabulaire des institutions indo-européennes*. Paris: Éditions de Minuit.
- Bernard, Paul, and Osmund Bopearachchi. 2002. "Deux bracelets grecs avec inscriptions grecques trouvés dans l'Asie centrale hellénisée." *Journal des Savants* 2: 237–278.
- Berranger, Danièle. 1983. "Le relief inscrit en l'honneur des Nymphes dans les carrières de Paros." *Revue des Etudes anciennes* 85 (3): 235–259.
- Bettarini, Luca. 2014. "Tra onomastica e poesia: rodio Ἰδαμενεύς in IG XII/1 737 (= CEG 459) e 904." *Glotta* 90: 46–70.
- . 2017. *Lingua e testo di Ipponatte*. Pisa: Fabrizio Serra.
- Bilgin, Tayfun. 2018. *Officials and Administration in the Hittite World*. Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter.
- Billerbeck, Margarethe, ed. 2006. *Stephani Byzantii Ethnica*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Billing, Oscar. 2024. Lycian A *erublije-* (eDiAna-ID 2241). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=2241> (accessed 07/09/2024).
- Billing, Oscar, David Sasseville, and Stefan Höfler. 2026. Proto-Anatolian **ne-ġnh₁-o-* (eDiAna-ID 3854). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3854> (accessed 06/01/2026).
- Blakely, Sandra. 2006. *Myth, Ritual, and Metallurgy in Ancient Greece and Recent Africa*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- . 2007. "Pherekydes' Daktyloi. Ritual, Technology, and the Presocratic Perspective." *Kernos* 20: 43–67.
- Bloom, Allan, ed. 1991. *The Republic of Plato*. New York: Basic Books.
- Blümel, Wolfgang. 1998–2012. "Einheimische Ortsnamen in Karien." *Epigraphica Anatolica* 30: 163–184. <https://wolfgang-bluemel.de/Downloads>.
- Bonati, Isabella. 2013. "Glosse esotiche nei frammenti di Ipponatte." In *Ricerche a confronto. Dialoghi di Antichità Classiche e del Vicino Oriente. Bologna – Trento, 2011*, edited by Viola Gheller, 29–42, 332–336. Montorso Vicentino: Edizioni Saecula.
- Borchhardt, Jürgen, Heiner Eichner, and Klaus Schulz. 2005. *Kerththi: oder der Versuch, eine antike Siedlung der Klassik in Zentrallykien zu identifizieren*. Antalya: Suna & İnan Kırac Research Institute on Mediterranean Civilizations.
- Borza, E. N., Brady Kiesling, R. Talbert, Sean Gillies, Jeffrey Becker, Tom Elliott, DARMC, G. Reger, R. Scott Smith, Greta Hawes, and Ryan Horne. 2026. Dardanos: a Pleiades place resource. *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places*. <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/501393>.
- Bousquet, Jean. 1975. "Arbinas, fils de Gergis, dynaste de Xanthos." *Comptes-rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 1: 138–150.
- . 1992. "Les inscriptions du Létôon en l'honneur d'Arbinas et l'épigramme grecque de la stèle de Xanthos." In *Fouilles de Xanthos. Tome IX. Volume 1*, edited by Henri Metzger, 155–199. Paris: Klincksieck.
- Bravo, Benedetto. 2009. "Erodoto e Pseudo-Erodoto sulla sterminata antichità degli egiziani." *Annali della Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa. Classe di Lettere e Filosofia* 1 (2): 623–647.
- Brelich, Angelo. 2010. *Gli eroi greci: un problema storico-religioso*. Milano: Adelphi.
- Bremmer, Jan N. 2009. "Zeus' Own Country: Cult and Myth in the Pride of Halicarnassus." In *Antike Mythen*, edited by Dill Ueli and Walde Christine, 292–312. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.
- Brixhe, Claude. 1976. *Le dialecte grec de Pamphylie*. Paris: Adrien-Maisonneuve.
- . 1987. *Essai sur le grec anatolien au début de notre ère*. Nancy: Presses universitaires de Nancy.

- . 1991. "Étymologie populaire et onomastique en pays bilingue." *Revue de philologie, de littérature et d'histoire anciennes* 65 (1): 67–82.
- . 1996. "Corpus des inscriptions dialectales de Pamphylie. Supplément IV." *Kadmos* 35 (1): 72–86.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/kadm.1996.35.1.72>. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/kadm.1996.35.1.72>.
- . 2010. "Linguistic Diversity in Asia Minor during the Empire: Koine and Non-Greek Languages." In *A Companion to the Ancient Greek Language*, edited by Egbert J. Bakker, 228–252. Chichester, West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell.
- . 2013. "La Pamphylie. Peuplement et dialecte: 40 ans de recherche." *Kadmos* 52 (1): 169–205.
- Brixhe, Claude, and Elsa Gibson. 1982. "Monuments from Pisidia in the Koç Collection." *Kadmos* 21 (2): 130–169.
- Brody, Lisa R. 2001. "The Cult of Aphrodite at Aphrodisias in Caria." *Kernos* (14): 93–109.
- Buck, Carl Darling. 1988. *A Dictionary of Selected Synonyms in the Principal Indo-European Languages*. Chicago-London: University of Chicago Press.
- Buckler, William Hepburn, and William Moir Calder. 1939. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua. Vol. VI. Monuments and Documents from Phrygia and Caria*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Buckler, William Hepburn, William Moir Calder, and W. K. C. Guthrie. 1933. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua. Vol. IV. Monuments and Documents from Eastern Asia and Western Galatia*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Cairns, Francis. 1995. "Horace, *Odes* 3. 7: Elegy, Lyric, Myth, Learning and Interpretation." In *Homage to Horace. A Bimillenary Celebration*, edited by S. J. Harrison, 65–99. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Calder, William Moir. 1956. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua. Vol VII. Monuments from Eastern Phrygia*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Calder, William Moir, J. M. R. Cormack, M. H. Ballance, and M. R. E. Gough. 1962. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua. Vol. VIII. Monuments from Lycaonia, the Pisido-Phrygian Borderland, Aphrodisias*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Campbell, Dennis R. M. 2008. "The Old Hurrian Verb." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 49: 75–92.
- Cancik, Hubert. 1990. "Größe und Kolossalität als religiöse und ästhetische Kategorien: Versuch einer Begriffsbestimmung am Beispiel von Statius, *Silve* I 1: *Ecus maximus Domitiani imperatoris*." *Visible Religion* 7: 51–68.
- Carruba, Onofrio. 1964. "Ahhijawa e altri nomi di popoli e di paesi dell'Anatolia occidentale." *Athenaeum* 42: 269–298.
- . 1980. "Review of *The Hittite Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago* by Hans G. Güterbock and Harry A. Hoffner, The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, Vol. 3, Fasc. 1, 1980." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 22: 358–365.
- Cassanmagnago, Cesare, ed. 2009. *Esiodo. Tutte le opere e i frammenti. Con la prima traduzione degli Scolii*. Milano: Bompiani.
- Çevik, Nevzat. 2003. "New Rock-Cut Tombs at Etenna and The Rock-Cut Tomb Tradition in Southern Anatolia." *Anatolian Studies*: 97–116.
- Chaniotis, Angelos. 2010. "Aphrodite's Rivals: Devotion to Local and Other Gods at Aphrodisias." *Cahiers Glotz* 21: 235–248.
- Chaniotis, Angelos, and Felipe Rojas. 2016. "A Second Lydian Inscription from Aphrodisias." In *Aphrodisias Papers 5: Excavation and Research at Aphrodisias, 2006-2012*, edited by Roland R. R. Smith, Julia Lenaghan, Alexander Sokolicek and Katherine Welch, 342–345. Portsmouth, Rhode Island: Journal of Roman Archaeology Supplement 103.
- Chantraine, Paul. 1931. "Grec κολοσσος." *Bulletin de l'Institut français d'archéologie orientale*: 449–452.
- Chiai, Gian Franco. 2009. "Allmächtige Götter und fromme Menschen im ländlichen Kleinasien der Kaiserzeit." *Millennium* 6 (1): 61–106.
- . 2020. *Phrygien und seine Götter. Historie und Religionsgeschichte einer anatolischen Region von der Zeit der Hethiter bis zur Ausbreitung des Christentums*. Vol. 1. Rahden/Westf.: Verlag Marie Leidorf.
- Chuvin, Pierre. 1991. *Mythologie et géographie dionysiaques. Recherches sur l'oeuvre de Nonnos de Panopolis*. Clermont-Ferrand: Adosa.
- Collins, Billie Jean. 1990. "The Puppy in Hittite Ritual." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 42 (2): 211–226.
- . 2004. "A Channel to the Underworld in Syria." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 67 (1): 54–56.
- Cordani, Violetta. 2016. "The Development of the Hittite Iron Industry. A Reappraisal of the Written Sources." *Die Welt des Orients* 46 (2): 162–176.
- Cornelius, Friedrich. 1958. "Geographie des Hethiterreiches (Schluss)." *Orientalia* 27 (4): 373–398.
- Corsten, Thomas. 2002. *Die Inschriften von Kibyra*. Bonn: R. Habelt.
- Corsten, Thomas, R. W. V. Catling, and Marijana Riel, eds. 2010. *A Lexicon of Greek Personal Names. Volume V.A. Coastal Asia Minor: Pontos to Ionia*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Coşkun, Yaşar. 1969. "Boğazköy Metinlerinde Geçen Başlıca Libasyon Kapları." *Ankara Üniversitesi Dil ve Tarih-Coğrafya Fakültesi Dergisi* 27 (3-4): 1–61.
- Cotticelli-Kurras, Paola. 2016. "Das semantische Feld der hethitischen Verwaltungssprache." In *Audias fabulas veteres. Anatolian Studies in Honor of Jana Součková-Siegelová*, edited by Šárka Velhartická, 71–97. Leiden-Boston: Brill.

- Cuypers, Martine. 2018. "Dei(1)ochos (BNJ 471)." *Jacoby Online. Brill's New Jacoby, Part III. [Scholarly edition]*, edited by Ian Worthington. Leiden: Brill.
- Czyzewska, Izabella Sylwia. 2012. "How to Pray to Hittite Gods: A Semantic and Contextual Analysis of Hittite Prayer Terminology with the New Editions of Selected Prayers of Muršili II." PhD, Department of Near and Middle East Studies, London: University of London.
- Dagron, Gilbert, and Denis Feissel. 1987. *Inscriptions de Cilicie*. Paris: De Boccard.
- Dale, Alexander. 2015. "Walwet and Kukalim." *Kadmos* 54 (1-2): 151–166.
- . 2020. "Gyges and Delphi: Herodotus 1.14." *The Classical Quarterly* 70 (2): 518–523.
- Dardano, Paola. 2016. "Su alcune espressioni ittite per 'vedere, osservare'." In *Anatolica et indogermanica. Studia linguistica in honorem Johannis Tischler septuagenarii dedicata*, edited by Henning Marquardt, Silvio Reichmuth and J. Virgilio García Trabazo, 43–61. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachen und Literaturen der Universität Innsbruck.
- Daubner, Frank. 2013. "Katakekaumene." *The Encyclopedia of Ancient History*, edited by Roger S. Bagnall, Kai Brodersen, Craige B. Champion, Andrew Erskine and Sabine R. Huebner. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444338386.wbeah14146>.
- Davies, Anna Morpurgo. 1975. "Negation and Disjunction in Anatolian - and Elsewhere." *Anatolian Studies* 25: 157–168.
- de Martino, Stefano. 1983. "La posizione del coppiere presso la corte ittita." *Studi classici e orientali* 32: 305–318.
- . 2017. "Central West: Philology." In *Hittite Landscape and Geography*, edited by Mark Weeden, Lee Z. Ullmann and Zenobia Homan, 253–261. Leiden: Brill.
- De Vaan, Michiel. 2008. *Etymological Dictionary of Latin and the Other Italic Languages*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- De Vries, Bert. 1967. "The Style of Hittite Epic and Mythology." PhD, Department of Mediterranean Studies, Waltham, MA: Brandeis University.
- Debord, Pierre. 1985. "La Lydie du nord-est." *Revue des Études Anciennes* 87 (3): 345–358.
- del Monte, Giuseppe F. 1986. "E gli dei camminano davanti a me...!" *Egitto e Vicino Oriente* 9: 59–70.
- . 2003. *Antologia della letteratura ittita*. Pisa: Servizio Editoriale Universitario di Pisa.
- del Monte, Giuseppe F., and Johann Tischler. 1978. *Répertoire Géographique des Textes Cunéiformes VI. Die Orts- und Gewässernamen der hethitischen Texte*. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- Della Casa, Romina. 2019. "A Problem of Meaning: Variations in Hittite Landscape as Narrated in the Sun-god's *mugawar* (CTH 323)." In *Hrozný and Hittite. The First Hundred Years. Proceedings of the International Conference Held at Charles University, Prague, 11–14 November 2015*, edited by Ronald I. Kim, Jana Mynářová and Peter Pavúk, 484–498. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Dercksen, Jan Gerrit. 2007. "On Anatolian Loanwords in Akkadian Texts from Kültepe." *Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und Vorderasiatische Archäologie* 97 (1): 26–46.
- Detienne, Marcel. 1986. *The Creation of Mythology*. Chicago-London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Di Bella, Fabiano Fiorello. 2018. "Portraits of Satraps and Tyrants in the Age of Peisistratos: Aristocratic Ideology as a Vehicle of Artistic Models in the Eastern Mediterranean." In *Approaches to Greek and Latin Language, Literature and History. Κατὰ σχολήν*, edited by Sandra Rodríguez Piedrabuena, Kádas. Gréta, Sara Macías Otero and Kevin Zilverberg, 259–279. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Dickie, Matthew W. 1996. "What is a *Kolossos* and how were *Kolossoi* made in the Hellenistic Period?" *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies* 37 (3): 237–257.
- Dietz, Albert. 2019. "Deity or Cult Statue? The Storm-God of Aleppo in the Visual Record of the Second Millennium BCE." In *Ancient Near Eastern Temple Inventories in the Third and Second Millennia BCE. Integrating Archaeological, Textual, and Visual Sources. Proceedings of a Conference Held at the LMU Centre for Advanced Studies, November 14–15, 2016*, edited by Jean M. Evans, Elisa Roßberger and Paola Paoletti, 189–206. Gladbeck: Pewe-Verlag.
- Dinçol, Ali, and Belkis Dinçol. 2008. "Die Prinzen- und Beamtsiegel aus der Oberstadt von Bogazkoy-Hattusa vom 16. Jahrhundert bis zum Ende des Grossreichszeit." Mainz: Philipp von Zabern.
- Dolcetti, Paola, ed. 2004. *Ferecide di Atene. Testimonianze e frammenti*. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso.
- Donner, Herbert, and Wolfgang Röllig, eds. 1971–1976. *Kanaanaische und Aramaische Inschriften. Mit einem Beitrag von O. Rössler. Dritte unveränderte Auflage*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- , eds. 2002. *Kanaanaische und Aramaische Inschriften. Band 1. 5., erweiterte und überarbeitete Auflage*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Dothan, M. 1985. "A Phoenician Inscription from 'Akko." *Israel Exploration Journal* 35 (2/3): 81–94.
- Drigo, Jasmim Sedie. 2024. "i-stem Adjectives in Indo-European." Doctoral Dissertation, Department of Linguistics, Ithaca, NY: Cornell University.
- Ducat, Jean. 1976. "Fonctions de la statue dans la Grèce archaïque: *kouros* et *kolossos*." *Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique* 100 (1): 239–251.
- Dunkel, George E. 2014. *Lexikon der indogermanischen Partikeln und Pronominalstämme*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- Eckhardt, Benedikt. 2019. "Some Aspects of the History of Private Associations in the Ancient Levant." *Ancient society* (49): 1–39.
- Euler, Katrin, and David Sasseville. 2019. "Die Identität des lydischen *Qldāns* und seine kulturgeschichtlichen Folgen." *Kadmos* 58 (1-2): 125–156.

- Evans, J. A. S. 1985. "Candaules whom the Greeks name Myrsilus..." *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies* 26 (3): 229.
- Falk, Harry. 1993. "Zur Wurzel *il* im Sanskrit und Pali." In *Comparative-Historical Linguistics: Indo-European and Finno-Ugric. Papers in Honor of Oswald Szemerényi III*, edited by Bela Brogyanyi and Reiner Lipp, 203–216. Amsterdam-Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Fatih, Onur. 2023. "The Western Shores of the Pamphylian Gulf: Tenedos, 'Olbia and Others' Revisited." *Phaselis* 9: 15–40.
- Favi, Federico. 2024. "Attic in the Flesh: The Language of Late Attic Comedy and its Atticist Reception." In *Ancient Greek Purism. I: The Roots of Atticism*, edited by Olga Tribulato, Federico Favi and Lucia Prauscello, 224–355. Berlin-Boston: de Gruyter.
- Feissel, Denis. 2010. "Noms épichoriques et géographie: deux notes d'onomastique isaurienne." In *Le tribù romane. Atti della XVIe Rencontre sur l'épigraphie (Bari 8–10 ottobre 2009)*, edited by M. Silvestrini, 423–426. Bari: Edipuglia.
- Fontrier, Aristote. 1892. "Le Monastère de Lembos près de Smyrne et ses possessions au XIIIe siècle (pl. XVIII)." *Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique* 16: 379–410.
- Forlanini, Massimo. 1977. "L'Anatolia nordoccidentale nell'impero eteo." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* XVIII: 197–223.
- . 1987. "Toponymie antique d'origine hattite?" *Bibliothèque des Cahiers de l'Institut de Linguistique de Louvain* 37: 105–122.
- . 2013a. "How to Infer Ancient Roads and Itineraries from Heterogeneous Hittite Texts: the Case of the Cilician (Kizzuwatnean) Road System." *Kaskal* 10: 1–34.
- . 2013b. "Les routes du Palâ." In *De Hattuša à Memphis. Jacques Freu in honorem*, edited by Michel Mazoyer and Sydney Hervé Aufrère, 43–58. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- . 2018. "La route des «Portes Ciliciennes» et ses embranchements avant l'âge classique." In *Topography and Toponymy in the Ancient Near East. Perspectives and Prospects*, edited by Jan Tavernier, Elynn Gorris, Kathleen Abraham and Vanessa Boschloss, 19–50. Leuven-Louvain-la-Neuve: Peeters-Université Catholique de Louvain.
- Foss, Clive, S. Mitchell, DARMC, R. Talbert, Sean Gillies, Johan Åhlfeldt, Jeffrey Becker, and Tom Elliott. 2017. Etenna: a Pleiades place resource. *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places*. <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/6388320> (accessed 1 April 2026).
- Foss, Clive, S. Mitchell, DARMC, R. Talbert, Sean Gillies, Tom Elliott, and Jeffrey Becker. 2019. *Orpeena. *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places*. <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/639027> (accessed 19 July 2024).
- Foss, Clive, S. Mitchell, R. Talbert, T. Elliott, and S. Gillies. 2012. Erymna: a Pleiades place resource. *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places*. <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/638831> (accessed 05 April 2026).
- Foss, Clive, S. Mitchell, R. Talbert, Ryan Horne, Jeffrey Becker, Sean Gillies, Richard Talbert, and Tom Elliott. 2024. Katenneis: a Pleiades place resource. *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places*. <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/638907> (accessed 01 April 2026).
- Francia, Rita. 2019. "Fra cucina e medicina. Spezie e piante aromatiche nell'Anatolia ittita." In *La via delle spezie. Come l'Oriente ha 'aromatizzato' l'Occidente. Atti di convegno. Milano, Biblioteca Ambrosiana, 19 settembre 2015*, edited by Elena Asero, 125–150. Roma: Aracne.
- . 2020. "Hittite *parhuena*-:'oats'?" *Oriens antiquus* 2: 131–139.
- Freu, Jacques. 1987. "Problèmes de chronologie et de géographie hittites: Madduwatta et les débuts de l'empire." *Hethitica* 8: 123–175.
- . 2001. "De l'indépendance à l'annexion: Le Kizzuwatna et Le Hatti aux XVIe et XVe siècles avant notre ère." In *La Cilicie: espaces et pouvoirs locaux (IIe millénaire av. J.-C. – IVe siècle ap. J.-C.). Actes de la Table Ronde d'Istanbul, 2-5 novembre 1999*, edited by Eric Jean, Ali M. Dinçol and Serra Durugönül, 13–36. Beyoğlu-Istanbul: Institut Français d'Études Anatoliennes-Georges Dumézil.
- . 2006. "Les montagnes dans l'historiographie et la géographie hittites." *Res Antiquae* 3: 219–243.
- Frick, Frank S. 1971. "The Rechabites Reconsidered." *Journal of Biblical Literature* 90 (3): 279–287.
- Friedrich, Paul. 1963. "An Evolutionary Sketch of Russian Kinship." In *Language and Culture. Proceedings of the 1962 Annual Spring Meeting of the American Ethnological Society*, edited by V. E. Garfield and W. L. Chafe, 1–26. Seattle: University of Washington Press.
- Fuscagni, Francesco. 2017. Rituale der Ayatarša, Wattitti und Šušumaniga (CTH 390). *hethiter.net/: CTH 390 (INTR 2017-03-06)*. https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/intro.php?xst=CTH%20390&prgr=%C2%A7%201&lg=DE&ed=F.%20Fuscagni.
- Gaál, Ernő. 1972. "The Economic Life of Alalah in the 18—17th Centuries BC." *Annales Universitatis Scientiarum Budapestinensis* 13: 279–300.
- . 1982. "State and Private Sectors in Alalah VII." *Acta antiqua Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 30 (1-4): 3–44.
- Gagné, Renaud. 2006. "What is the Pride of Halicarnassus?" *Classical Antiquity* 25 (1): 1–33.
- García Trabazo, J. Virgilio. 2024. "Hittite Divinities of the Underworld and the Night Goddess of Šamuḫa: An Interpretation from their Hybrid Cosmological Background." In *Gods and Languages in Ancient Anatolia*, edited by Mariona Vernet, Ignasi-Xavier Adiego, José Virgilio García Trabazo, María-Paz de Hoz and Bartomeu Obrador-Cursach, 33–53. Barcelona: Edicions de la Universitat de Barcelona.

- Garnier, Romain. 2021. "Lord Qldāns and related forms." *Historische Sprachforschung* 135 (1): 182–214.
- Garnier, Romain, and Benoît Sagot. 2020. "New Results on a Centum Substratum in Greek: the Lydian Connection." In *Loanwords and Substrata. Proceedings of the Colloquium Held in Limoges (June 5th-7th 2018)*, edited by Romain Garnier, 169–200. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität Innsbruck.
- Gates, Henry Phelps. 1971. *The Kinship Terminology of Homeric Greek*. Baltimore: Waverly Press.
- Gérard, Raphaël. 2005. *Phonétique et morphologie de la langue lydienne*. Leuven: Peeters Publishers.
- Gessel, Ben H. L. van 1998–2001. *Onomasticon of the Hittite Pantheon*. Leiden: Brill.
- Girbal, Christian. 2002. "Zum hattischen Lexikon." *Altorientalische Forschungen* 29 (2): 249–287.
- Giusfredi, Federico. 2010. *Sources for a Socio-economic History of the Neo-Hittite States*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- Godefroy, Frédéric. 1901. *Lexique de l'ancien français*. Edited by J. Bonnard and Am. Salmon. Paris-Leipzig: H. Welter.
- Godley, A. D. 1975. *Herodotus. Books I and II*. Cambridge, MA-London: Harvard University Press-William Heinemann.
- Goedegebuure, Petra. 2024. "The Luwian Word for 'City, Town'." *Anatolian Studies* 74: 47–73.
- Goetze, Albrecht. 1947. "Contributions to Hittite lexicography." *Journal of cuneiform studies* 1 (4): 307–320.
- . 1953. "The Theophorous Elements of the Anatolian Proper Names from Cappadocia." *Language* 29 (3): 263–277.
- . 1962. "Cilicians." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 16 (2): 48–58.
- Görke, Susanne, and Sabine Melzer. 2016. hethiter.net/: CTH 480.1 (TRde 10.02.2016). https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/translatio.php?xst=CTH%20480.1&expl=&lg=DE&ed=S.%20G%C3%B6rke%20%20Melzer.
- Grayson, Kirk A. 1996. *Assyrian Rulers of the Early First Millennium BC II (1114-859 BC)*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Guldager Bilde, Pia, ed. 2024. *Mouldmade Bowls of the Black Sea Region and Beyond: From Prestige Object to an Article of Mass Consumption*. Edited by Susan I. Rotroff. Leiden: Brill.
- Gürel, Betül, Aykan Akçay, and Nihal Önen. 2019. "Phaselis Teritoryumu nda Kolalemis ve Ailesine Ait *Khamosorion* ve Çiftlik Yerleşimi / Kolalemis and his Family's *Khamosorion* and Farm Settlement found in the Territory of Phaselis." *Phaselis* 5: 413–424.
- Gusmani, Roberto. 1964. *Lydisches Wörterbuch. Mit grammatischer Skizze und Inschriftensammlung*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- . 1968. "Zur Deutung einiger milyischer Wörter." *Archiv Orientalní* 36: 1–18.
- . 1972. "Lydische Siegelaufschriften und Verbum Substantivum." *Kadmos* 11 (1): 47–54.
- . 1975. "Die lydische Sprache." *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 107 (2): 134–142.
- . 1979. "Zwei lydische Inschriften aus Sardis." *Kadmos* 18 (1): 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.1515/kadm.1979.18.1.71>.
- . 1980. *Lydisches Wörterbuch. Mit grammatischer Skizze und Inschriftensammlung. Ergänzungsband. Lieferung 1*. Heidelberg: Winter.
- Güterbock, Hans G. 1957. "Review of *Hethitisches Wörterbuch. Kurzgefasste kritische Sammlung der Deutungen hethitischer Wörter* by Johannes Friedrich." *Oriens* 10 (2): 350–362.
- Haag, H. 1999. "*bēn*." In *Theological Dictionary of The Old Testament*, edited by Johannes G. Botterweck and Harold Ringgren, 145–159. Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans.
- Haas, Volkert. 1994. *Geschichte der hethitischen Religion*. Leiden: Brill.
- . 2003. *Materia Magica et Medica Hethitica. Ein Beitrag zur Heilkunde im Alten Orient*. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.
- . 2006. *Die hethitische Literatur Texte, Stilistik, Motive*. Berlin; New York: De Gruyter.
- . 2008. *Hethitische Orakel vorzeichen und abwehrstrategien. Ein beitrag zur hethitischen Kulturgeschichte*. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.
- Hackstein, Olav. 2024. "Tocharian Lexemes for 'belly', 'beaming' and 'burly'." 43rd East Coast Indo-European Conference (ECIEC 43), University of Georgia, Athens.
- Hansen, Erik, and Christian Le Roy. 1976. "Au Létôon de Xanthos: les deux temples de Létô." *Revue Archéologique* 2: 317–336.
- Hansen, Mogens Herman, and Thomas Heine Nielsen. 2004. *An Inventory of Archaic and Classical Poleis*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hard, Robin. 2004. *The Routledge Handbook of Greek Mythology*. London-New-York: Routledge.
- Harder, Richard, ed. 1958. *Theodor Wiegand. Didyma. Zweiter Teil: Die Inschriften, von A. Rehm*. Berlin: Gebr. Mann.
- Hawkins, John David. 2000. *Corpus of Hieroglyphic Luwian Inscriptions. Volume I. Inscriptions of The Iron Age. Part 3*. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.
- Hawkins, John David, and Mark Weeden. 2017. "Kizzuwatna and the Euphrates States: Kummaha, Elbistan, Malatya Philology." In *Hittite Landscape and Geography*, edited by Mark Weeden, Lee Z. Ullmann and Zenobia Homan, 281–294. Leiden: Brill.
- Hawkins, Shane. 2013. *Studies in the Language of Hipponax*. Bremen: Hempen.
- Heberdey, Rudolf, ed. 1941. *Tituli Asiae Minoris collecti et editi auspiciis Academiae Litterarum Vindobonensis, vol. III. Tituli Pisidiae linguis Graeca et Latina conscripti, fasc. I. Tituli Termessi et agri Termessensis*. Vindobonae: Hoelder-Pichler-Tempsky.

- Hellenkemper, Hansgerd, and Friedrich Hild. 2004. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 8. Lykien und Pamphylien. Tabula Imperii Byzantini*. Wien: Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaft.
- Herbordt, Suzanne. 2005. *Die Prinzen- und Beamtsiegel der hethitischen Grossreichszeit auf Tonbullien aus dem Nişantepe-Archiv in Hattusa*. Mainz am Rhein: von Zabern.
- Herrmann, Peter, and Kemal Ziya Polatkan. 1969. *Das Testament des Epikrates und andere neue Inschriften aus dem Museum von Manisa*. Wien-Köln-Graz: Hermann Böhlhaus Nachf.
- Herrmann, Peter, and Fritz Schachermeyr, eds. 1981. *Tituli Asiae Minoris V. Tituli Lydiae linguis graeca et latina conscripti. Fasciculus I. Regio septentrionalis ad orientem vergens*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Hild, Friedrich. 2004. "Komai in Lykien." *Gephyra* 1: 119–126.
- Hild, Friedrich, and Hansgerd Hellenkemper. 1990. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 5. Kilikien und Isaurien*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Hild, Friedrich, and Marcell Restle. 1981. *Tabula Imperii Byzantini. 2. Kappadokien (Kappadokia, Charsianon, Sebasteia und Lykandos)*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Hoffner, Harry A., Jr. 1974. *Alimenta hethaeorum. Food Production in Hittite Asia Minor*. New Haven, Conn.: American Oriental Society.
- . 1980. "Histories and Historians of the Ancient Near East: The Hittites." *Orientalia* 49 (4): 283–332.
- . 1988. "A Scene in the Realm of the Dead." In *A Scientific Humanist. Studies in Memory of Abraham Sachs*, edited by Erle Leichty, Maria deJ. Ellis and Pamela Gerardi, 191–199. Philadelphia: Samuel Noah Kramer Fund.
- . 1996. "From Head to Toe in Hittite: the Language of the Human Body." In *'Go to the Land I Will Show You'. Studies in Honor of Dwight W. Young*, edited by Joseph E. Coleson and Victor H. Matthews, 247–259. Winona Lake, Indiana: Eisenbrauns.
- . 1997. *The Laws of the Hittites. A Critical Edition*. Leiden-New York-Köln: Brill.
- . 2000. "Thoughts on a New Volume of a Hittite Dictionary." Review of Hittite Etymological Dictionary, Vol. 4: Words Beginning with K, Jaan Puhvel. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 120 (1): 68–75.
- . 2003. "On a Hittite Lexicographic Project." *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 123 (3): 617–625.
- Hoffner, Harry A., Jr., and Gary Beckman. 1990. *Hittite Myths*. Atlanta: Scholars Press.
- Hoffner, Harry A., Jr., and H. Craig Melchert. 2024. *A Grammar of the Hittite Language. Part 1: Reference Grammar*. 2 ed. University Park, PA: The Pennsylvania State University Press.
- Högemann, Peter. 2000. "Der Iliasdichter, Anatolien und der griechische Adel." *Klio* 82 (1): 7.
- Högemann, Peter, and Norbert Oettinger. 2018. *Lydien. Ein altanatolischer Staat zwischen Griechenland und dem Vorderen Orient*. Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter.
- Holthausen, Ferdinand. 1912. "Etymologien." *Indogermanische Forschungen* 30: 47–49.
- Hooker, Mischa 2017. *John Lydus. On the Months (De mensibus)*
<https://archive.org/details/JohnLydusOnTheMonthsTr.Hooker2ndEd.2017>.
- Hornblower, Simon. 2015. *Lykophron: Alexandra*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Horowitz, Wayne. 1998. *Mesopotamian Cosmic Geography*. Winona Lake, Indiana: Eisenbrauns.
- Houwink ten Cate, Philo Hendrik J. 1961. *The Luwian Population Groups of Lycia and Cilicia Aspera During the Hellenistic Period*. Leiden: Brill.
- . 1966. "Mursilis' Northwestern Campaigns-Additional Fragments of His Comprehensive Annals." *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 25 (3): 162–191.
- . 1970. *The Records of the Early Hittite Empire (C. 1450-1380 BC)*. Leiden: Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten.
- Huld, Martin, and James P. Mallory. 1997. "Pot." In *Encyclopedia of Indo-European Culture*, edited by James P. Mallory and Douglas Q. Adams, 443–446. London-Chicago: Fitzroy Dearborn.
- Hunter, Richard, and Rebecca Laemmle. 2019. "Enkelados: Callimachus Fragment 1.36." *Classical Philology* 114 (3): 493–498.
- Hutter, Manfred. 1988. *Behexung, Entsühnung und Heilung: das Ritual der Tunnawiya für ein Königspaar aus mittelhethitischer Zeit : (KBo XXI 1 - KUB IX 34 - KBo XXI 6)*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- Iancu, Liviu Mihail. 2023. "'Who is Gyges?' Once Again: Assessing the Carian Connections of the First Mermnad King of Lydia." In *Studies on the History and Archaeology of Lydia from the Early Lydian Period to Late Antiquity*, edited by Ergün Laflı and Guy Labarre, 149–168. Besançon: Presses universitaires de Franche-Comté.
- Imparati, Fiorella. 2004. *Studi sulla società e sulla religione degli Ittiti*. Firenze: LoGisma.
- Ingarao, Giovanni. 2020. "Erodoto linguista? L'origine dei nomi degli dèi greci." *Hormos* 12: 248–269.
- Jonnes, Loyd 2002. *The Inscriptions of the Sultan Dagi I: Philomelion, Thymbrion/Hadrianopolis, Tyraion*. Bonn: Habelt.
- Jurczyk, Thomas. 2022. *The Notion of »holy« in Ancient Armenian Texts from the Fifth Century CE. A Comparative Approach Using Digital Tools and Methods*. Bielefeld: Bielefeld University Press.
- Kalinka, Ernst. 1901. *Tituli Asiae Minoris. Conlecti et editi auspiciis Caesareae Academiae Litterarum Vindobonensis. Volumen I. Tituli Lyciae. Lingua Lycia conscripti*. Wien: Hölder.
- , ed. 1920–1944. *Tituli Asiae Minoris. Collecti et editi auspiciis Academiae litterarum Vindobonensis. Volumen II. Tituli Lyciae. Linguis graeca et latina conscripti*. Wien: R. M. Rohrer.

- Karvounis, Christos. 2008. *Aussprache und Phonologie im Altgriechischen*. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.
- Karwiese, Stefan. 1991. "The Artemisium Coin Hoard and the First Coins of Ephesus." *Revue belge de numismatique et de sigillographie* 137: 1–28.
- Kearns, John Michael. 1994. "A Greek Genitive from Lydia." *Glotta* 72: 5–14.
- Kempinski, Aharon, and Silvin Košak. 1970. "Der Išmeriga-Vertrag." *Die Welt des Orients* 5 (2): 191–217.
- Killen, Simone. 2008. "Die Doppelaxt als Parasemon von Tenedos." In *Vom Euphrat bis zum Bosphorus. Kleinasien in der Antike. Festschrift für Elmar Schwertheim zum 65. Geburtstag*, edited by Engelbert Winter, 367–372. Bonn: Habelt.
- Kimball, Sara E. 1994. "The IE Short Diphthongs *oi, *ai, *ou and *au in Hittite." *Die Sprache* 36 (1): 1–28.
- Kisbali, Tamás Péter. 2020. "Two Faces and Many Interpretations: a Note on the Janiform Coinage of Tenedos." *Numismatica e Antichità Classiche* 49: 27–37.
- Klengel, Horst. 1965. "Der Wettergott von Halab." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 19 (3): 87–93.
- . 1998. *Geschichte des hethitischen Reiches*. Leiden: Brill.
- Kloekhorst, Alwin. 2008a. *Etymological Dictionary of the Hittite Inherited Lexicon*. Leiden: Brill.
- . 2008b. "Studies in Lycian and Carian Phonology and Morphology." *Kadmos* 47: 117–146.
- . 2010. "Initial Stops in Hittite (with an Excursus on the Spelling of Stops in Alala Akkadian)." *Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und vorderasiatische Archäologie* 100: 197–241.
- Knapp, F. P. 1974. "Wiederum germanisches ē." *Beiträge zur Geschichte der deutschen Sprache und Literatur* 96 (Jahresband): 207–240.
- Konuk, Koray. 2009. "Erbina in Caria?" In *Ancient History, Numismatics and Epigraphy in the Mediterranean World. Studies in Memory of Clemens E. Bosch and Sabahat Atlan and in Honour of Nezahat Baydur*, edited by Oğuz Tekin and Aliye Erol, 212–218. Istanbul: Ege Publications.
- Konuk, Koray, and Michael Kerschner. 2020. "Electrum Coins and Their Archaeological Context: The Case of the Artemision of Ephesus." In *White Gold. Studies in Early Electrum Coinage*, edited by Peter van Alfen and Ute Wartenberg, 83–175. New York-Jerusalem: The American Numismatic Society and The Israel Museum.
- Kronasser, Heinz. 1960. "κολο- 'groß'." *Die Sprache* 6: 172–178.
- Külzer, Andreas. 2020. "In the Shadow of Mount Ida (Kaz Dağı): Roads and Settlements in the Southern Troad during Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages." In *Propontis ve Çevre Kültürleri / Propontis and Surrounding Cultures*, edited by Vedat Keleş, 585–596. İstanbul: Ege Yayınları.
- Laird, Andrew. 2001. "Ringing the Changes on Gyges: Philosophy and the Formation of Fiction in Plato's Republic." *The Journal of Hellenic Studies* 121: 12–29.
- Lane, Eugene N. 1971–1978. *Corpus Monumentorum Religionis Dei Menis*. Leiden: Brill.
- . 1975. "Two Notes on Lydian Topography." *Anatolian Studies* 25: 105–110.
- Lane Fox, Robin. 2009. *Travelling Heroes: In the Epic Age of Homer*. London: Penguin Books.
- Laroche, Emmanuel. 1946. "Recherches sur les noms des dieux hittites." *Revue Hittite et Asiatique* 7 (46): 7–139.
- . 1959. *Dictionnaire de la langue louvite*. Paris: Maisonneuve.
- . 1966. *Les noms des Hittites*. Paris: Klincksieck.
- . 1973. "Études de linguistique anatolienne." *Revue Hittite et Asiatique* 31: 83–99.
- . 2016. *Études anatoliennes*. Edited by Alfonso Archi and Hatice Gonnet. Turnhout: Brepols.
- Lavelle, Brian M. 1997. "Epikouros and epikouroi in Early Greek Literature and History." *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies* 38 (3): 229–262.
- Leaf, Walter. 1923. *Strabo on the Troad: book XIII, cap. I*. Cambridge: The University Press.
- Lebrun, René. 1981. *Hymnes et prières hittites*. Louvain-la-Neuve: Centre d'histoire des religions.
- . 1990. "Notes de lexicologie lycienne." *Hethitica* 10: 161–170.
- Lebrun, René. 1976. *Samuha, foyer religieux de l'empire hittite*. Louvain-la-Neuve: Institut orientaliste Université catholique de Louvain.
- Lejeune, Michel. 1972. *Phonétique historique du mycénien et du grec ancien*. Paris: Klincksieck.
- Leloux, Kevin. 2018. "La Lydie d'Alyatte et Crésus. Un royaume à la croisée des cités grecques et des monarchies orientales. Recherches sur son organisation interne et sa politique extérieure." Phd, Liege: Université de Liege.
- Levick, Barbara, Stephen Mitchell, James Potter, and Marc Waelkens, eds. 1993. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua, Vol. X. Monuments from the Upper Tembris Valley, Cotiaenum, Cadi, Synaus, Ancyra, and Tiberiopolis recorded by C.W.M. Cox, A. Cameron, and J. Cullen*. London: Society for the Promotion of Roman Studies.
- Levine, Baruch A. 1963. "The *neṯnīm*." *Journal of Biblical Literature* 82 (2): 207–212.
- Li Gotti Macri, Maria Vittoria. 1976. "Καβηλλέες δὲ οἱ Μηίονες." *Helikon* 15-16: 486–495.
- Liddell, Henry George, and Robert Scott. 1996. *A Greek-English Lexicon. Revised and Augmented throughout by Sir Henry Stuart Jones with the Assistance of Roderick McKenzie et al. With a Revised Supplement*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Lipiński, Edward. 1975. *Studies in Aramaic Inscriptions and Onomastics. I*. Leuven: Leuven University Press.
- Lloyd-Jones, Hugh. 1999. "The Pride of Halicarnassus." *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*: 1–14.
- Mackie, C. J. 2014. "Zeus and Mount Ida in Homer's Iliad." *Antichthon* 48: 1–13.
- Magni, Elisabetta. 2017. "Suffix Borrowing and Conflict Through Latin-Greek Hybrid Formations." *Pallas* 103: 283–292.

- Malay, Hasan. 1994. *Greek and Latin Inscriptions in the Manisa Museum*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Mallory, James P., and Douglas Q. Adams, eds. 1997. *Encyclopedia of Indo-European Culture*. London-Chicago: Fitzroy Dearborn.
- Marcuson, Hannah Leigh. 2016. "'Word of the Old Woman': Studies in Female Ritual Practice in Hittite Anatolia." Doctoral Dissertation, Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, Chicago: The University of Chicago.
- Martínez-Rodríguez, Elena. 2025. "Lydian and the Languages of the Achaemenid Empire." In *Contacts of Languages and Peoples in the Hittite and Post-Hittite World. Volume 2, The 1st Millennium and the Eastern Mediterranean Interface*, edited by Federico Giusfredi, Alvise Matessi, Stella Merlin and Valerio Pisaniello, 157–172. Leiden: Brill.
- Mastin, B. A. 1979. "Was The šālīš the Third Man in the Chariot?" In *Studies in the Historical Books of the Old Testament*, edited by J. A. Emerton, 125–154. Leiden: Brill.
- Matthews, Roger, and Claudia Glatz. 2009. "The Historical Geography of North-Central Anatolia in the Hittite Period: Texts and Archaeology in Concert." *Anatolian Studies* 59: 51–72.
- Mazoyer, Michel. 2004. "Défense et illustration du Hatti: les divinités hatties et la fondation CTH 726.1." *Colloquium Anatolicum* 3: 53–66.
- McCabe, Donald F. 1991. The Princeton Project on the Inscriptions of Anatolia. In *The PHI Epigraphy Project*. Princeton: The Institute for Advanced Study.
- Mehl, A. 2003. "Xanto il Lido, i suoi Lydiaka e la Lidia." In *Licia e Lidia prima dell'ellenizzazione. Atti del Convegno internazionale, Roma, 11-12 ottobre 1999*, edited by Mario Giorgieri, Mario Salvini, Marie-Claude Tremouille and Paolo Vannicelli, 239–263. Roma: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche.
- Melchert, H. Craig. 1987. "PIE Velars in Luvian." In *Studies in Memory of Warren Cowgill (1929-1985). Papers from the Fourth East Coast Indo-European Conference. Cornell University, June 6-9, 1985*, edited by Calvert Watkins, 182–204. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.
- . 1990. "Adjectives in *-iyo- in Anatolian." *Historische Sprachforschung* 103 (2): 198–207.
- . 1991. "The Lydian Emphasizing and Reflexive Particle -ś/-is." *Kadmos* 30 (2): 131–142.
- . 1997. "Luvian /tāna-/ 'sanctified, inviolable'." *Historische Sprachforschung* 110 (1): 47–51.
- . 1999. "Two Problems of Anatolian Nominal Derivation." In *Compositiones Indogermanicae in memoriam Jochem Schindler*, edited by Einer Eichner and Hans Christian Luschützky, 365–375. Prague: Enigma.
- . 2001. *Cuneiform Luvian Lexicon* <http://www.linguistics.ucla.edu/people/Melchert/webpage/LUVLEX.pdf>.
- . 2004. *A Dictionary of the Lycian Language*. Ann Arbor: Beech Stave Press.
- . 2012a. "Genitive Case and Possessive Adjective in Anatolian." In *Per Roberto Gusmani 1. Linguaggi, culture, letteratura 2. Linguistica storica e teorica. Studi in ricordo*, edited by Giampaolo Borghello and Vincenzo Orioles, 273–286. Udine: Forum.
- . 2012b. "Luvo-Lycian Dorsal Stops Revisited." *The Sound of Indo-European 2. Papers on Indo-European Phonetics, Phonemics and Morphophonemics*: 206–218.
- . 2013. Naming Practices in Second- and First-Millennium Western Anatolia. <https://linguistics.ucla.edu/people/Melchert/Naming%20Practices%20in%20Second%20and%20First%20Millennium%20Western%20Anatolia%20adjusted.pdf>.
- . 2014a. "Anatolian Nominal Stems in *-(C)o-." In *Das Nomen im Indogermanischen. Morphologie, Substantiv versus Adjektiv, Kollektivum. Akten der Arbeitstagung der Indogermanischen Gesellschaft vom 14. bis 16. September 2011 in Erlangen*, edited by Norbert Oettinger and Thomas Steer, 205–214. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- . 2014b. "PIE *-eh₂ as an 'Individualizing' Suffix and the Feminine Gender." In *Studies on the Collective and Feminine in Indo-European from a Diachronic and Typological Perspective*, edited by Sergio Neri and Roland Schuhmann, 257–271. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- . 2018. "Hittite *tit(ta)nu-*, *titti-*, and Lycian *stta*." *Chatreššar* 11 (1): 25–33.
- . 2019. "The Anatolian Hieroglyphic Signs L 41, L 172 and L 319= L 416." In *'And I Knew Twelve Languages'. A Tribute to Massimo Poetto on the Occasion of His 70th Birthday*, edited by Natalia Bollati-Guzzo and Piotr Taracha, 356–377. Warsaw: Agade Bis-University of Warsaw-Faculty of Oriental Studies.
- . 2021. "A Possible New Greco-Carian Contact Phenomenon." In *Linguistic and Cultural Interactions between Greece and Anatolia*, 108–115. Brill.
- . 2024. *A Dictionary of Cuneiform Luvian*. Ann Arbor, MI: Beech Stave Press.
- Mendelsohn, Isaac. 1940. "Guilds in Ancient Palestine." *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 80 (1): 17–21.
- Mendez Dosuna, Julián. 2008. "Fonética." In *Veinte años de Filología Griega (1984-2004)*, edited by Francisco R. Adrados, José A. Berenguer Sánchez, Eugenio R. Luján and Juan Rodríguez Somolinos, 313–341. Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas.
- Méndez Dosuna, Julián. 1988. "La evolución del diptongo 'oi' en beocio." *Emerita* 56: 25–35.
- Méndez Dosuna, Julián. 2021. "The Pronunciation of Upsilon and Related Matters." In *The Early Greek Alphabets. Origin, Diffusion, Uses*, edited by Robert Parker and Philippa M. Steele, 119–145. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Meriggi, Piero. 1935. "Die erste Person Singularis im Lydischen." *Revue Hittite et Asiatique* 3 (19-20): 69–116.

- Miller, D. Gary. 2013a. *Ancient Greek Dialects and early Authors. Introduction to the Dialect Mixture in Homer, with Notes on Lyric and Herodotus*. Boston-Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Miller, Jared L. 2010. "Practice and Perception of Black Magic among the Hittites." *Altorientalische Forschungen* 37 (2): 167–185.
- . 2013b. *Royal Hittite Instructions and Related Administrative Texts*. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature.
- Milner, Nicholas P. 1998. *An Epigraphical Survey in the Kibyra-Olbasa Region Conducted by A.S. Hall*. Ankara: British Institute of Archaeology.
- Mitchell, Stephen. 1970. "Wer waren die Gottesfürchtigen?" *Chiron* 28: 55–64.
- Mitten, David Gordon, and Güldem Yügrüm. 1971. "The Gygean Lake, 1969: Eski Balikhane, Preliminary Report." *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology* 75: 191–195.
- Monier-Williams, M. 1899. *A Sanskrit-English Dictionary Etymologically and Philologically Arranged. With Special Reference to Cognate Indo-European Languages*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Montanari, Franco. 2015. *The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Morani, Moreno. 2001. "La terminologia del 'sacro' in lingue indeuropee antiche: riflessioni e problemi." In *Pensiero e istituzioni del mondo classico nelle culture del Vicino Oriente. Atti del Seminario Nazionale di studio (Brescia, 14-15-16 ottobre 1999)*, edited by Rosa Bianca Finazzi and Alfredo Valvo, 165–195. Alessandria: Edizioni Dell'Orso.
- Mouton, Alice. 2010. "Sorcellerie hittite." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 62 (1): 105–125.
- . 2015. "Les rituels de la Vieille Femme Tunnawiya: témoignages du Bas Pays hittite?" In *La Cappadoce méridionale de la Préhistoire à l'époque byzantine. 3e Rencontres d'archéologie de IFEA, Istanbul 8-9 novembre 2012*, edited by Aksel Tibet, Olivier Henry and Dominique Beyer, 79–90. Istanbul: Institut français d'études anatoliennes.
- Mouton, Alice, and Yiğit Erbil. 2020. "Dressing Up for the Gods: Ceremonial Garments in Hittite Cultic Festivals according to the Philological and Archaeological Evidence." *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 20 (1): 48–86.
- Mouton, Alice, and Ilya Yakubovich. 2019. "Internal or External evil: a Merism in Luwian Incantations." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 82 (2): 209–231.
- Munk Højte, Jakob. 2008. "The Cities That Never Were. Failed Attempts at Colonization in the Black Sea." In *Meetings of Cultures in the Black Sea Region*, edited by Pia Guldager Bilde and Jane Hjarl Petersen, 149–162. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.
- Müseler, Wilhelm. 2019. "Opponents and Successors of the Xanthian Dynasty in Western Lycia: The Weḫssere Questions Reconsidered." *Gephyra* 17: 29–81.
- Müseler, Wilhelm, and Diether Schürr. 2018. "Zur Chronologie in den Inschriften auf dem Agora-Pfeiler von Xanthos (TL 44), den betroffenen Dynasten und ihren Münzen." *Klio* 100 (2): 381–406.
- Mylius, Klaus. 2005. *Sanskrit-Deutsch. Deutsch-Sanskrit Wörterbuch*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Napolitano, Maria Luisa. 2005. "Tenedo, Lesbo e la porta della Troade." In *Eoli ed Eolide tra madrepatria e colonia*, edited by Alfonso Mele, Maria Luisa Napolitano and Amedeo Visconti, 201–260. Napoli: Luciano Editore.
- Neu, Erich. 1974. *Der Anitta-Text*. Vol. 18 *Studien zu den Boğazköy-Texten*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 1996. *Das hurritische Epos der Freilassung I. Untersuchungen zu einem hurritisch-hethitischen Textensemble aus Hattusa*. Vol. 31 *Studien zu den Boğazköy-Texten*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag.
- Neumann, Günter. 1969. "Lydisch-hethitische Verknüpfungen." *Athenaeum* 47: 217–225.
- . 1979. "Zum Namen Kilikien." In *Studia Mediterranea Piero Meriggi Dicata*, edited by Onofrio Carruba, 429–437. Pavia: Gianni Iuculano Editore.
- . 1991. "Hethitisch *negna*- 'Bruder'." *Historische Sprachforschung* 104 (1): 63–66.
- . 1994a. *Ausgewählte kleine Schriften*. Edited by Enrico Badali, Helmut Nowicki and Susanne Zeilfelder. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität.
- . 1994b. "Wertvorstellungen und Ideologie in den Personennamen der mykenischen Griechen." *Anzeiger der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften* 131: 127–166.
- Neumann, Günter, and Johann Tischler. 2007. *Glossar des Lykischen*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Nicolle, Raphaël. 2015. "Les dieux de l'Orage à Rome et chez les Hittites. Étude de religion comparée." PhD, Histoire et archéologie des mondes anciens, Nanterre: Université Paris-Ouest Nanterre.
- Niehr, Herbert, and Paolo Xella. 2021. *Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Phoenician Culture II.1: Religion - Deities and Mythical Characters*. Leuven-Paris-Bristol: Peeters.
- Nollé, Johannes. 1984. "Etenna: ein Vorbericht." *Epigraphica Anatolica* 3: 143.
- . 1991. "Pamphyliche Studien 11 und 12." *Chiron* 21: 331–344.
- . 1992. "Zur Geschichte der Stadt Etenna in Pisidien." *Forschungen in Pisidien, Asia Minor Studien* 6: 61–141.
- . 2016. "Beiträge zur kleinasiatischen Münzkunde und Geschichte: 12. Mastaura am Fuße der Mesogis – Überlegungen zu den Patriatraditionen einer wenig bekannten antiken Polis." *Gephyra* 13: 49–82.
- Nollé, Johannes, and Friedel Schindler. 1991. *Die Inschriften von Selge*. Bonn: Habelt.
- Noonan, Benjamin J. 2019. *Non-Semitic Loanwords in the Hebrew Bible. A Lexicon of Language Contact*. University Park, PA: Eisenbrauns.
- Norbruis, Stefan. 2021. *Indo-European Origins of Anatolian Morphology and Semantics. Innovations and Archaisms in Hittite, Luwian and Lycian*. Amsterdam: LOT.

- Novák, Mirko, and Susanne Rutishauser. 2012. "Tuthaliya, Šunaššura und die Grenze zwischen Ḫatti und Kizzuwatna." In *Altorientalische Studien zu Ehren von Pascal Attinger. mu-ni u₄ ul-li₂-a-aš ḡa₂-ḡa₂-de₃*, edited by Catherine Mittermayer and Sabine Ecklin, 259–269. Fribourg-Göttingen: Academic Press-Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- Oettinger, Norbert. 1976. *Die militärischen eide der Hethiter*. Vol. 22 *Studien zu den Boğazköy-Texten*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 1989/1990. "Die 'dunkle Erde' im Hethitischen und Griechischen: Alfred Heubeck zum Gedächtnis (20.7. 1914–24.5. 1987)." *Die Welt des Orients* 20/21: 83–98.
- . 2021. "Language Contact between Lydian and Greek or the Origin of Lydian *k*." In *Linguistic and Cultural Interactions between Greece and Anatolia. In Search of the Golden Fleece*, edited by Michele Bianconi, 116–130. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Olmo Lete, Gregorio del, and Joaquín Sanmartín. 2015. *A Dictionary of the Ugaritic Language in the Alphabetic Tradition*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Olshin, Benjamin B. 2019. *Lost Knowledge. The Concept of Vanished Technologies and Other Human Histories*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Otten, Heinrich. 1950. "Die Gottheit Lelvani der Boğazköy-Texte." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 4 (2): 119–136.
- Özgümüş, Ferudun. 2014. "Afrodisias'taki Semitik Kültür Üzerine Bazı düşünceler." In *Arkeolojiyle Geçen Bir Yaşam İçin Yazılar Veli Sevin'e Armağan. Scripta. Essays in Honour of Veli Sevin A Life Immersed in Archaeology*, edited by Aynur Özfırat, 355–361. İstanbul: Ege Yayınları.
- Palaima, Thomas G. 1999. "Mycenaean Militarism from a Textual Perspective. Onomastics in Context: *lāwos, dāmos, klewos*." In *Polemos. Le contexte guerrier en Égée à l'âge du Bronze. Actes de la 7e Rencontre égéenne internationale Université de Liège, 14 -17 avril 1998. II*, edited by Robert Laffineur, 367–379. Liège: Université de Liège.
- Payne, Annick, Anna Bauer, Elisabeth Rieken, and Thomas Steer. 2026. Common Luwian /zunni-(ti)/ (eDiAna-ID 789). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=789> (accessed 04/03/2026).
- Payne, Annick, Anna Bauer, David Sasseville, and Olav Hackstein. 2026. Proto-Anatolian **ne* (eDiAna-ID 3145). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3145> (accessed 15/01/2026).
- Pecchioli Daddi, Franca. 1982. *Mestieri, professioni e dignità nell'Anatolia ittita*. Roma: Edizioni dell'Ateneo.
- . 2004. "Palace Servants and Their Obligations." *Orientalia* 73 (4): 451–468.
- Pecchioli Daddi, Franca, and Anna Maria Polvani. 1990. *La mitologia ittita*. Brescia: Paideia.
- Petzl, Georg. 2007. *Tituli Lydiae Linguis Graeca et Latina Conscripti. Fasciculus III. Philadelphieia et ager Philadelphenus*. Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- Pisano, Carmine. 2011a. "Antropologia della regalità nella Grecia antica. Hermes, lo scettro, l'ariete." PhD, Storia antica, Napoli: Università degli Studi di Napoli 'Federico II'.
- . 2011b. "Gradi di alterità e logiche di «traduzione»: il caso di Hermes/Candaule." In *Les représentations des dieux des autres*, edited by Corinne Bonnet, Amandine Declercq and Iwo Slobodzianek, 51–64. Caltanissetta: Salvatore Sciascia Editore.
- Polomé, Edgar C., and James P. Mallory. 1997. "Sacred." In *Encyclopedia of Indo-European Culture*, edited by James P. Mallory and Douglas Q. Adams, 493–494. London-Chicago: Fitzroy Dearborn.
- Polvani, Anna Maria. 1991. "KBo XXVI 136: una versione del mito della scomparsa del dio Sole." In *Quattro studi ittiti*, edited by Fiorella Imparati, 69–75. Firenze: LoGisma.
- Popko, Maciej. 1991. "Eine 'Schwarze Tafel' aus Bogazköy (KUB LX 121)." *Altorientalische Forschungen* 18 (2): 239–245.
- . 2002. "Zum Tempel des Teššup von Ḫalap in Ḫattuša." *Altorientalische Forschungen* 29 (1): 73–80.
- . 2009. *Arinna. Eine heilige Stadt der Hethiter*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Posani, Claudia. 2023. "Alcune considerazioni sull'iscrizione luvio-geroglifica TELL AHMAR 2 e sull'episodio erodoteo di Gige e Candaule: i verba videndi e le connotazioni etico-sociali della vergogna connessa alla nudità." In *Shaping Boundaries. Ethnicity and Geography in the Eastern Mediterranean Area (First Millennium BC). Proceedings of the 15th Melammu Workshop, Verona, 19–21 January 2022*, edited by Simonetta Ponchia and Luisa Prandi, 197–213. Münster: Zaphon.
- Pozza, Marianna. 2023. "An Overview of the Hittite Suffix *-ena/-ina-*: a Preliminary Assessment." *Rivista degli studi orientali* 96 (2/4): 227–242.
- Puhvel, Jaan. 1984–. *Hittite Etymological Dictionary*. Berlin-New York: Mouton-De Gruyter.
- . 1992. "Philology and Etymology, with Focus on Anatolian." In *Reconstructing Languages and Cultures*, edited by Edgar C. Polomé and Werner Winter, 265–270. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- . 2011. "Barm and Balm, Hittite Style." *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 63 (1): 103–104.
- Ramsay, William Mitchell, ed. 1906. *Studies in the History and Art of the Eastern Provinces of the Roman Empire. Written for the Quatercentenary of the University of Aberdeen by Seven of its Graduates*. Aberdeen: Aberdeen University Press.
- Réveilhac, Florian. 2023. "Anatolian Names in °ασητας/°ασατης/°ασατας, CLuw. **aššatta-*, Lyc. B **asata-* and Lyc. A *ahata*." *News from the Lands of the Hittites* 7: 195–211.
- . 2024. "In the Name of Gods. In Search of Divine Epithets Through Luwic Personal Names." In *What's in a Divine Name? Religious Systems and Human Agency in the Ancient Mediterranean*, edited by Alaya Palamidis and Corinne Bonnet, 471–488. Leiden-Boston: De Gruyter.

- Ricl, Marijana. 1991. "Hosios kai Dikaios. Première partie: Catalogue des inscriptions." *Epigraphica Anatolica* 19: 1–70.
- . 2010. "A New Inscription from the Cayster Valley and the Question of Supernomina in Hellenistic and Roman Lydia." In *In Onomatologos. Studies in Greek Personal Names Presented to Elaine Matthews*, edited by R. W. V. Catling and F. Marchand, 530–551. Oxford: Oxbow Books.
- Rieken, Elisabeth. 1999. *Untersuchungen zur nominalen Stammbildung des Hethitischen*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 2003. "Hieroglyphen-luwisch *zí+ra/i-la-mi-i* („SCALPRUM.ARGENTUM“) *su-ha-pa-na-ti*: ein Kompositum und eine neue luwisch-lateinische Isoglosse." *Historische Sprachforschung* 116 (1): 35–53.
- . 2019. "On Several Old and New Etymologies and the Alleged Diphthongization of * *ē* > *iya* in Hittite and Luwian." In *Luwic Dialects and Anatolian: Inheritance and Diffusion*, edited by Ignasi-Xavier Adiego, José Virgilio García Trabazo, Mariona Vernet, Bartomeu Obrador-Cursach and Elena Martínez Rodríguez, 215–226. Barcelona: Edicions de la Universitat de Barcelona.
- . 2022a. Cuneiform Luwian *warpann(i)-* (eDiAna-ID 2188). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=2188> (accessed 04/09/2024).
- . 2022b. Cuneiform Luwian *warpašša-(i)* (eDiAna-ID 2132). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=2132> (accessed 15/09/2024).
- . 2026a. Cuneiform Luwian *nānašri(ya)-* (eDiAna-ID 3858). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3858> (accessed 12/01/2026).
- . 2026b. Cuneiform Luwian *šāla-* (eDiAna-ID 3058). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3058> (accessed 05/04/2026).
- Rieken, Elisabeth, Jürgen Lorenz, Anna Bauer, and Susanne Görke. 2009. CTH 323.1 - Vom Verschwinden und der Wiederkehr der Sonnengottheit. *hethiter.net/: CTH 323.1 (INTR 2009-08-12)*. https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_myth/translatio.php?xst=CTH%20323.1&expl=&lg=DE&ed=E.%20Rieken%20et%20al.
- Rieken, Elisabeth, and David Sasseville. 2014. "Social Status as a Semantic Category of Anatolian: The Case of PIE **yo-*." In *Munus amicitiae. Norbert Oettinger a collegis et amicis dicatum*, edited by H. Craig Melchert, Elisabeth Rieken and Thomas Steer, 302–314. Ann Arbor-New York: Beech Stave Press.
- . 2024. Proto-Luwic **mEulād̥r/n-* (eDiAna-ID 1731). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1731> (accessed 18/08/2024).
- Rieken, Elisabeth, David Sasseville, and Thomas Steer. 2026. Proto-Anatolian **lala-* (eDiAna-ID 792). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=792> (accessed 19/01/2026).
- Rieken, Elisabeth, and Ilya Yakubovich. 2022. "Zu den Reflexen der Wurzel **al-* in den anatolischen Sprachen." In *Zurück zur Wurzel. Struktur, Funktion und Semantik der Wurzel im Indogermanischen. Akten der 15. Fachtagung der Indogermanischen Gesellschaft vom 13. bis 16. September 2016 in Wien*, edited by Melanie Malzahn, Hannes A. Fellner and Theresa-Susanna Illés, 267–280. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- Rignanese, Giuseppe. 2018. "Erodoto, i *piromi*, il *kalos kagathos*. Alcuni spunti di riflessione." In *Dialoghi sull'Archeologia della Magna Grecia e del Mediterraneo. Atti del II Convegno Internazionale di Studi. Paestum, 28-30 giugno 2017*, edited by Marina Cipriani, Angela Pontrandolfo and Michele Scafuro, 377–386. Paestum: Fondazione Paestum-Pandemos.
- Ritter, Hans-Werner. 1964. *Sylloge nummorum Graecorum. Deutschland. Sammlung v. Aulock. H. 9 = 3329 - 4040. Phrygien*. München: Hirmer.
- Rix, Helmut, Martin Kümmel, Thomas Zehnder, Reiner Lipp, and Brigitte Schirmer, eds. 2001. *Lexikon der indogermanischen Verben*. Wiesbaden: Ludwig Reichert Verlag.
- Robert, Jeanne, and Louis Robert. 1972. "Bulletin épigraphique." *Revue des Études Grecques* 85 (406-408): 364–526.
- Robert, Louis. 1962. *Villes d'Asie mineure*. Paris: De Boccard.
- . 1963. *Noms indigènes dans l'Asie-Mineure gréco-romaine*. Vol. 1. Paris: Maisonneuve.
- . 1978. "Les conquêtes du dynaste lycien Arbinas." *Journal des savants* 1 (1): 3–48.
- . 1980. *A travers l'Asie Mineure. Poètes et prosateurs, monnaies grecques, voyageurs et géographie*. Athènes: École française d'Athènes.
- . 1982. "Documents d'Asie Mineure. XXI. Au Nord de Sardes. I. Lycophron et le marais d'Echidna, Strabon et le lac de Koloè." *Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique* 106 (1): 334–352.
- Robertson, Noel. 1982. "Hittite Ritual at Sardis." *Classical Antiquity* 1 (1): 122.
- Rojas, Felipe. 2016. "Kings from the Deep: The Lydian Lakes and the Archaeological Imagination1." In *Cultural Memories in the Roman Empire*, edited by John H. D. Alcock, Karl Galinsky and Kenneth Lapatin, 191–205. Los Angeles: Getty Trust Publications.
- Roosevelt, Christopher H. 2009. *The Archaeology of Lydia, from Gyges to Alexander*. 1. publ. ed. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Rosi, Susanna. 1984. "Il ruolo delle 'truppe' UKU. UŠ nell'organizzazione militare ittita." *Studi Miceni ed Egeo-Anatolici* 24: 109–129.
- Roth, Martha T., Robert D. Biggs, John A. Brinkman, Miguel Civil, Walter Farber, Erica Reiner, and Matthew W. Stolper, eds. 1956–2010. *The Assyrian Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago*. Chicago: The Oriental Institute.
- Roux, Georges. 1960. "Qu'est-ce qu'un *κολοσσός*? Le «colosse» de Rhodes; Les «colosses» mentionnés par Eschyle, Hérodote, Théocrite et par diverses inscriptions." *Revue des Études Anciennes* 62 (1-2): 5–40.

- Rüster, Christel, and Gernot Wilhelm. 2012. *Landschenkungsurkunden hethitischer Könige*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Rutherford, Ian. 2020. *Hittite Texts and Greek Religion. Contact, Interaction, and Comparison*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Rybolt, John E. 1971. "-aster, a Latin Suffix." *Classical Folia* 25: 303–319.
- Şahin, Mehmet Çetin, ed. 1981. *Die Inschriften von Stratonikeia. Teil I: Panamara*. Bonn: Habelt.
- Santini, Marco. 2016. "A Multi-Ethnic City Shapes Its Past: The 'Pride of Halikarnassos' and the Memory of Salmakis." *Annali della Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa. Classe di Lettere e Filosofia* 8 (1): 3–35.
- . 2017. "Bellerophon, Pegasos and the Foundation of Halikarnassos. Contributions to the Study of the Salmakis Inscription." *Studi Classici e Orientali* 63: 109–144.
- Sasseville, David. 2020. *Anatolian Verbal Stem Formation. Luwian, Lycian and Lydian*. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- . 2024. Lycian A *hāta-* (eDiAna-ID 3499). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3499> (accessed 21/06/2024).
- . 2025. Lydian *τorsa-* (eDiAna-ID 2406). <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=2406> (accessed 18/03/2025).
- . 2026. Cuneiform Luwian *armann(i)-* (eDiAna-ID 3228). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3228> (accessed 13/01/2026).
- Sasseville, David, and Stefan Höfler. 2026. Cuneiform Luwian *aldann(i)-* (eDiAna-ID 3800). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3800> (accessed 13/01/2026).
- Sasseville, David, and Thomas Steer. 2026. Proto-Anatolian **hles-r-* (eDiAna-ID 744). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=744> (accessed 12/01/2026).
- Saviano, Martina. 2017–2018. "Usi e contesti della scrittura genealogica: il caso di Kar." *Incontri di filologia classica* 17: 197–213.
- Schmitt, Rüdiger. 1982. "Iranische Wörter und Namen im Lykischen." In *Serta Indogermanica. Festschrift für Günter Neumann zum 60. Geburtstag*, edited by Johann Tischler, 373–388. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität Innsbruck.
- Schniedewind, William M. 2013. *A Social History of Hebrew: Its Origins through the Rabbinic Period*. New Haven-London: Yale University Press.
- Schuler, Einar von. 1969. "*marnu'ātum* - ein kleinasiatisches Lehnwort im Altassyrischen." In *Lišan mithurti. Festschrift Wolfram Freiherr von Soden zum 19. VI. 1968 gewidmet von Schülern und Mitarbeitern*, edited by Wolfgang Röllig, 317–322. Kevelaer-Neukirchen-Vluyn: Butzon & Bercker-Neukirchener Verlag des Erziehungsvereins.
- Schuler, Einar von 1980–1983. "Lelwani." In *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*, edited by Erich Ebeling, et al., 595–598. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Schürr, Diether. 1997. "Luwisch-lykische Wettergottformeln." *Die Sprache* 39 (1): 59–73.
- . 2006. "Elf lydische Etymologien." In *Studi linguistici in onore di Roberto Gusmani*, edited by Raffaella Bombi, Guido Cifoletti, Fabiana Fusco, Lucia Innocente and Vincenzo Orioles, 1569–1587. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso.
- . 2012. "Der lykische Dynast Arttumbara und seine Anhänger." *Klio* 94 (1): 18–44.
- . 2016a. "Vermutungen zum Namen Mastaura." *Gephyra* 13: 83–85.
- . 2016b. "Von Leto, Fröschen und so weiter. Brückenschläge zwischen Versailles und Hattusa." In *Vir Doctus Anatolicus. Studies in Memory of Sencer Şahin / Sencer Şahin Anısına Yazılar*, edited by Yayınma Hazırlayanlar, Burak Takmer, Ebru N. Akdoğu Arca and Nuray Gökalp Özdil, 761–779. Kuzgun Yayınevi: İstanbul.
- . 2018. "Zum Agora-Pfeiler in Xanthos VI: das Westgedicht auf Cheriga und Muni (TL 44d)." *Kadmos* 57 (1-2): 55–106.
- . 2019. "Lykische Schwiegereöhne." *Kadmos* 58 (1-2): 185–192.
- . 2021. "Eine lykische Opferformel." *Gephyra* 22: 15–23.
- Schwemer, Daniel. 2005–2006. "Lehnbeziehungen zwischen dem Hethitischen und dem Akkadischen." *Archiv für Orientforschung* 51 (2): 220–234.
- Sekunda, Nicholas Victor. 1996. "Anatolian War-Sickles and the Coinage of Etenna." In *Studies in Ancient Coinage from Turkey*, edited by Richard Ashton, 9–18. London: British Institute of Archeology at Ankara.
- Servais, Jean. 1965. "Le «colosse» des Cypsélides." *L'Antiquité Classique* 34 (1): 144–174.
- Sesoldi, Andrea. 2019. "Zii e nipoti in latino e germanico: arcaismo o innovazione?" *Studi e Saggi Linguistici* 57 (1): 129–154.
- Sichelschmidt, Vera. 2019. "Statuen und visuelle Kommunikation im Ionien archaischer Zeit." PhD, Philosophischen Fakultät, Freiburg: Albert-Ludwigs-Universität.
- Simon, Zsolt. 2015. "Zur vorgriechischen Geschichte von Imbros aus philologischer Sicht." *Ancient West & East* 14: 1–21.
- . 2019. "Zu den karisch-griechischen Lehnbeziehungen." *Glotta* 95 (1): 295–308.
- . 2022. Ancient Greek γύγη (eDiAna-ID 1522). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1522> (accessed 22/03/2025).
- . 2023. "(DEUS)ma-ru-ti-ka-sa pu-ti-ti-sa – Musings on a Hieroglyphic Luwian Phrase." In *By God's Grace. Ancient Anatolian Studies Presented to Aram Kosyan on the Occasion of his 65th Birthday*, edited by Yervand H.

- Grekyan, In Ancient Anatolian Studies Presented to Aram Kosyan on the Occasion of his 65th Birthday, 337–346. Turnhout: Peeters.
- . 2026. Carian **urom* > **u/wrm* (eDiAna-ID 3303). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3303> (accessed 06/03/2026).
- Singer, Itamar. 1994. "Concepts of the Other in Near Eastern Religions." In *The Thousand Gods of Hatti: The Limits of an Expanding Pantheon*, edited by Ilai Alon, Ithamar Gruenwald and Itamar Singer, 81–102. Leiden- New York-Köln: Brill.
- Smith, Kirby Flower. 1920. "The Literary Tradition of Gyges and Candaules." *The American Journal of Philology* 41 (1): 1–37.
- Snell, Bruno. 1955–2010. *Lexikon des frühgriechischen Epos*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht.
- Soysal, Oguz. 2024. "Kleine Beiträge zu den unpublizierten Bo-Texten (IV)." *KASKAL*: 105–120.
- Soysal, Oğuz. 2019. "Hethitische Festbeschreibungen aus den Grabungskampagnen 2015 und 2017 in Kayalıpınar (Samuḫa)." In *Keilschrifttafeln aus Kayalıpınar I*, edited by Elisabeth Rieken, In Textfunde aus den Jahren 1999–2017, 157–190. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 2021. "Ein religiöses Konzept und seine Übermittlung zwischen zwei Sprachen Altanatoliens." *Die Welt des Orients* 51 (2): 165–173.
- Soysal, Oğuz, and Süel Aygül. 2016. "The Hittian-Hittite Foundation Rituals From Ortaköy (II). Fragments to CTH 726. 'Rituel bilingue de fondation d'un temple ou d'un palais.'" In *Audias fabulas veteres. Anatolian Studies in Honor of Jana Součková-Siegelová*, edited by Šárka Velhartická, 320–364. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Specht, Edith. 2001. "Tenedos und Tennes: Zur fruher Geschichte der Insel." *Hyperboreus* 7 (1-2): 25–36.
- Spina, Luigi. 1999. "Riscrivere 'Candaule'." *Rhetorica* 17 (2): 111–136.
- Starke, Frank. 1990. *Untersuchungen zur Stammbildung des keilschrift-luwischen Nomens*. Vol. 31 *Studien zu den Boğazköy-Texten*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Stefanini, Ruggero. 1983. "Review of *The Hittite Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago* (CHD). Vol. 3, Fasc. 1 (From *la-/lai-* to *-ma*, by H. G. Güterbock & H. A. Hoffner." Review of *The Hittite Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago* (CHD). Vol. 3, Fasc. 1 (From *la-/lai-* to *-ma*), Hans G. Güterbock, Harry A. Hoffner. *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 42 (2): 143–151.
- Steitler, Charles W. 2017. *The Solar Deities of Bronze Age Anatolia. Studies in Texts of the Early Hittite Kingdom*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 2019. "Hittite Professionals and Patron Deities." In *Economy of Religions in Anatolia: From the Early Second to the Middle of the First Millennium BCE. Proceedings of an International Conference in Bonn (23rd to 25th May 2018)*, edited by Manfred Hutter and Sylvia Hutter-Braunsar, 125–139. Münster: Ugarit-Verlag.
- . 2020. "Offerings to the *loci numinosi*: Distinctive Features of Sacred Spaces and Cult Practices." In *Cult, Temple, Sacred Spaces. Cult Practices and Cult Spaces in Hittite Anatolia and Neighbouring Cultures. Proceedings of the First International HFR Symposium, Mainz, 3–5 June 2019*, edited by Susanne Görke and Charles W. Steitler, 317–344. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 2023. "Solar and Chthonic Deities in Ancient Anatolia: The Evolution of the Chthonic Solar Deity in Hittite Religion." In *Theonyms, Panthea and Syncretisms in Hittite Anatolia and Northern Syria*, edited by Federico Giusfredi Livio Warbinek, 149–179. Firenze: Firenze University Press.
- Stempel, Reinhard. 1987. "Armenischen *surb* 'heilig, rein': Erbwort oder Lehnwort?" In *Nubia et Oriens Christianus. Festschrift für C. Detlef G. Müller zum 60. Geburtstag*, edited by Piotr O. Scholz and Reinhard Stempel, 239–244. Köln: Verlag Jürgen Dinter.
- Stivala, Gabriella. 2004. "Contributo alla lessicologia ittita: per una classificazione dei nomi di piante erbacee." *Studi epigrafici e linguistici sul Vicino Oriente antico* 21: 35–64.
- Strauss, Rita. 2006. *Reinigungsrituale aus Kizzuwatna: ein Beitrag zur Erforschung hethitischer Ritualtradition und Kulturgeschichte*. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Strubbe, Johan H. M. 1997. *Arai Epitymbioi. Imprecations Against Desecrators of the Grave in the Greek Epitaphs of Asia Minor. A Catalogue*. Bonn: Habelt.
- Süel, Aygül, and Mark Weeden. 2017. "Central East: Philology." In *Hittite Landscape and Geography*, edited by Mark Weeden, Lee Z. Ullmann and Zenobia Homan, 200–208. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- Talamo, Clara. 1979. *La Lidia arcaica*. Bologna: Patron.
- Talbert, Richard J. A. 2000. *Barrington Atlas of the Greek and Roman World: Map-by-Map Directory*. Princeton University Press.
- Taracha, Piotr. 2008. "The Storm-God and Hittite Great King." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 50: 745–751.
- . 2009. *Religions of Second Millennium Anatolia*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Tekin, Oğuz, and Aliye Erol-Özdizbay. 2015–2020. *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum. Turkey 9. The Özkan Arikantürk Collection*. Istanbul: Turkish Institute of Archaeology.
- Teppa, Serena. 2013. "Fratello, fratellanza e 'affratellamento'." *Historika* 3: 273–285.
- Thomas, François. 1940. "Le suffixe latin *-aster / -astrvm*." *Revue des Études Anciennes* 42 (1): 520–528.
- Thonemann, Peter, C Crowther, V., and E. Chiricat, eds. 2013. *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua. Vol. XI. Monuments from Phrygia and Lykaonia, Recorded by M. H. Ballance, W. M. Calder, A. S. Hall and R. D. Barnett*. London: Society for the promotion of Roman studies.
- Threatte, Leslie. 1980–1996. *The Grammar of Attic Inscriptions*. Berlin-New York: De Gruyter.

- Tischler, Johann. 1977–2016. *Hethitisches etymologisches Glossar*. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität.
- Tobler, Adolf. 1857–2002. *Altfranzösisches Wörterbuch*. Edited by Erhard Lommatzsch, Peter Blumenthal and Achim Stein. Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag.
- Torri, Giulia. 1999. *Lelwani. Il culto di una dea ittita*. Roma: Università degli Studi di Roma 'La Sapienza'.
- . 2003. *La similitudine nella magia analogica ittita*. Roma: Herder.
- . 2011. Rituale di costruzione di un tempio (CTH 726.1). *hethiter.net/*: CTH 726.1 (INTR 2017-01-12). https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/txhet_besrit/intro.php?xst=CTH%20726.1&prgr=&lg=IT&ed=G.%20Torri.
- Toynbee, Arnold J. 1910. "On Herodotus III. 90, and VII. 75, 76." *The Classical Review* 24 (8): 236–238.
- Trameri, Andrea. 2024. *Kizzuwatna. History of Cilicia in the Middle and Late Bronze Age (ca. 2000-1200 BC)*. Leiden: Brill.
- Trémouille, Marie-Claude. 2001. "Kizzuwatna, terre de frontière." *Publications de l'Institut Français d'Études Anatoliennes* 13 (1): 57–78.
- Tsagalīs, Christos. 2017. *Early Greek Epic Fragments I. Antiquarian and Genealogical Epic*. Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter.
- Tukey, Anne. 1962. "Kinship Terminology in the Romance Languages." PhD, Ann Arbor: University of Michigan.
- Tüner Önen, Nihal, and Murat Arslan. 2025. "New Epigraphic Evidence from the Territory of Phaselis: Funerary Inscriptions and Local Cults." *Gephyra* 30: 121–134.
- Ünal, Ahmet. 1996. *The Hittite Ritual of Ḫantitaššu from the City of Hurma Against Troublesome Years*. Ankara: Turkish Historical Society Printing House.
- . 1999. "A Hittite Foundation Ritual on the Occasion of Building a New Fortified Border Town." In *Studi e Testi II*, edited by Stefano De Martino and Fiorella Imparati, 213–223. Firenze: LoGisma.
- Valério, Miguel, and Ignasi-Xavier Adiego. 2024. "Carian *q* and Luwic **H*." In *Gods and Languages in Ancient Anatolia*, edited by Mariona Vernet, Ignasi-Xavier Adiego, José Virgilio García Trabazo, María-Paz de Hoz and Bartomeu Obrador-Cursach, 511–530. Barcelona: Ediciones de la Universidad de Barcelona.
- Valério, Miguel, and Ilya Yakubovich. 2022. "From 'Foreman' to 'Warlord': Royal Titles in Iron Age Western Anatolia." *Aula Orientalis* 40 (2): 345–353.
- Van Bremen, Riet. 2010. "Adrastos at Aphrodisias." In *Onomatologos. Studies in Greek Personal Names Presented to Elaine Matthews*, edited by R. W. V. Catling and F. Marchand, 440–455. Oxford: Oxbow Books.
- Van den Hout, Theo P. J. 1995. *Der Ulmitešub-Vertrag: eine prosopographische Untersuchung*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- . 2003. "Studies in the Hittite Phraseological Construction I: Its Syntactic and Semantic Properties." In *Hittite Studies in Honor of Harry A. Hoffner Jr. on the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, edited by Beckman Gary, H. Beal Richard and McMahon Gregory, 177–203. University Park, USA: Penn State University Press.
- Vandorpe, Katelijjn. 2000. "Negotiators' Laws from Rebellious Sagalassos in an Early Hellenistic inscription." In *Sagalassos V. Report on the Survey and Excavation Campaigns of 1996 and 1997*, edited by Marc Waelkens and Lieven Loots, 489–508. Leuven: Leuven University Press.
- Veenhof, Klaas Roelof. 1972. *Aspects of Old Assyrian Trade and Its Terminology*. Leiden: Brill.
- Vernant, Jean-Pierre. 2006. *Myth and Thought Among the Greeks*. New York: Zone Books.
- Visintin, Monica. 2000. "Echidna, Skythes e l'arco di Herakles. Figure della marginalità nella versione greca delle origini degli Sciti, Herodot. 4, 8-10." *Materiali e discussioni per l'analisi dei testi classici* 45: 43–81.
- Vita Barra, Juan Pablo. 2018. "Terminology related to Work Force and Job Categories in Ugarit." In *What's in a Name? Terminology Related to the Work Force and Job Categories in the Ancient Near East*, edited by Agnès Garcia-Ventura, 355–367. Tecklenburg: Ugarit-Verlag.
- Vitti, Mirella. 1984. "Ittito *lappina*-(^{SAR}) - ŠU.KIŠ^{SAR} 'ortica (?)'." *Studi Micenei ed Egeo-Anatolici* 24: 149–150.
- Von Soden, Wolfram. 1959–1981. *Akkadisches Handwörterbuch: unter Benutzung des lexikalischen Nachlasses von Bruno Meissner (1868-1947)*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- von Wartburg, Walther. 1934. *Französisches etymologisches Wörterbuch: eine darstellung des galloromanisches Sprachschatzes*. Vol. 3. Leipzig-Berlin: B.G. Teubner.
- Wallace, Robert W. 2006. "KUKALIM, WALWET, and the Artemision Deposit: Problems in Early Anatolian Electrum Coinage. Studies in Money and Exchange: Festschrift for Joh." In *Agoronomia. Studies in Money and Exchange Presented to John H. Kroll*, edited by Peter van Alfen, 37–48. New York: The American Numismatic Society.
- Watkins, Calvert. 1994. "Latin *suppus*." In *Selected Writings. Volume II: Culture and Poetics*, edited by Lisa Olivier, 499–504. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität Innsbruck.
- Watson, P. 1989. "*Filiaster*: *Privignus* or 'Illegitimate Child'?" *The Classical Quarterly* 39 (2): 536–548.
- Watson, Wilfred G. E. 2018. "Terms for Occupations, Professions and Social Classes in Ugaritic: An Etymological Study." *Folia Orientalia* 55: 307–378.
- West, Martin L., ed. 1966. *Hesiod. Theogony*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- . 1997. *The East Face of Helicon. West Asiatic Elements in Greek Poetry and Myth*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- . 2003. *Greek Epic Fragments from the Seventh to the Fifth Centuries BC*. Cambridge, MA-London: Harvard University Press.

- . 2011. *The Making of the Iliad: Disquisition and Analytical Commentary*. Oxford-New York: Oxford University Press.
- Witzak, Krzysztof Tomasz. 2006. "The Hittite Name for 'Garlic'." *Acta Orientalia Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 59 (3): 341–345.
- Woodard, Roger D. 2024. *Aeolic and Aeolians: Origins of an Ancient Greek Language and its Community of Speakers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wörrle, Michael. 1988. *Stadt und Fest im kaiserzeitlichen Kleinasien: Studien zu einer agonistischen Stiftung aus Oinoanda*. München: Beck.
- Wright, David P. 1987. *The Disposal of Impurity: Elimination Rites in the Bible and in Hittite and Mesopotamian Literature*. Atlanta, GE: Scholars Press.
- Yakubovich, Ilya. 2019. "The Mighty Weapon of Tarhunt." In *Over the Mountains and Far Away. Studies in Near Eastern History and Archaeology Presented to Mirjo Salvini on the Occasion of His 80th Birthday*, edited by Pavel S. Avetisyan, Roberto Dan and Yervand H. Grekyan, 544–559. Summertown, Oxford: Archaeopress Publishing.
- . 2021. "The Anatolian Connections of the Greek God Enyalios." In *Linguistic and Cultural Interactions between Greece and Anatolia. In Search of the Golden Fleece*, edited by Michele Bianconi, 233–245. Leiden-Boston: Brill.
- . 2024. "The Lydian god Q̌dāns." In *Gods and Languages in Ancient Anatolia*, edited by Marion Vernet, Ignasi-Xavier Adiego, José Virgilio García Trabazo, María-Paz de Hoz and Bartomeu Obrador-Cursach, 239–261. Barcelona: Ediciones de la Universidad de Barcelona.
- . 2026a. Lydian ēnwaḷa- (eDiAna-ID 1427). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=1427> (accessed 01/03/2026).
- . 2026b. Lydian mastā- (eDiAna-ID 3709). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=3709> (accessed 16/01/2026).
- Yakubovich, Ilya, and Zsolt Simon. 2024. Common Luwian /tawīyan(ni)/ (eDiAna-ID 234). *eDiAna*. <http://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/dictionary.php?lemma=234> (accessed 18/09/2024).
- Zadok, Ran. 1985. *Geographical Names According to New- and Late-Babylonian Texts*. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- Zehnder, Thomas. 2010. *Die hethitischen Frauennamen. Katalog und Interpretation*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Zehner, Joseph. 2024. "Anchoring Genealogy: Hecataeus of Miletus, Pherecydes of Athens, and Herodotus." *Mnemosyne* 77 (2): 197–216.
- Zgusta, Ladislav. 1955. "Lydian Interpretations." *Archív Orientální* 23 (4): 510–544.
- . 1964a. *Anatolische Personennamensippen*. Prag: Tschechoslowakischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- . 1964b. *Kleinasiatische Personennamen*. Prag: Tschechoslowakische Akademie der Wissenschaften.
- . 1970. *Neue Beiträge zur kleinasiatischen Anthroponymie*. Prag: Academia.
- . 1984. *Kleinasiatische Ortsnamen*. Heidelberg: Winter.